

Advanced nanomaterials for Li- ion battery, Photocatalytic dye degradation and Nitrite sensing studies

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Certificate

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “**ADVANCED NANOMATERIALS FOR LI- ION BATTERY, PHOTOCATALYTIC DYE DEGRADATION AND NITRITE SENSING STUDIES**” submitted by **PAVITRA V.** to SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY for the award of the degree of Doctor of Philosophy is a Bonafede record of the research work carried out by her under our supervision and guidance. The content of the thesis, in full or parts have not been submitted to any other institute or university for the award of any degree or diploma.

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I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this thesis are original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This thesis is my own work and does not contain any outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements.

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SYNOPSIS

1. TITLE: “ADVANCED NANOMATERIALS FOR LI- ION BATTERY, PHOTOCATALYTIC DYE DEGRADATION AND NITRITE SENSING STUDIES”

2. INTRODUCTION

Nanoscience and nanotechnology related to the synthesis, characterization, exploration, exploitation, and utilization of nanostructured materials, are done in which nanomaterials are in 1 nm (10^{-9} m) range at least in one dimension. Such nanostructured systems constitute a bridge between single molecules and infinite bulk systems. Individual nanostructures involve clusters, nanoparticles, nanocrystals, quantum dots, nanowires, and nanotubes, while collections of nanostructures involve arrays, assemblies, and superlattices of individual nanostructures [1]. The chemical and physical properties of nanomaterials can significantly differ from those of the atomic-molecular or the bulk materials of the same chemical composition. The uniqueness of the structural characteristics, energetic response, dynamics, and chemistry of nanostructures is novel and constitutes the experimental and conceptual background for the novel field of nanoscience. The semiconducting materials at nanoscale are widely used for the manufacturing of various electronic, electrical and photovoltaic devices owing to their unique band structure, optical properties, good charge mobility and ability to absorb photons from light. The choice of semiconductor is governed by the conduction band energy and density of states, which facilitates the charge separation and minimizes the recombination. Secondly, the high surface area and morphology of semiconductors is important for maximizing the light absorption by the dye molecules, while maintaining good electrical connectivity with the substrate [2-4].

Energy is an essential material basis for human survival. The energy crisis is escalating with concerns of the global warming and environmental pollution caused by the rapid exhaustion of non-renewable fossil fuels and aggravation of environment problems, there is increasing interest in developing energy transition from natural, renewable and clean energy such as, wind, solar, biomass, tide and geothermal is becoming more and more important [5]. In rechargeable batteries, Li-ion batteries (LIBs) acts as power sources for a diverse range of applications, including not only portable energy storage devices but also electric vehicles (EVs) and hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs). In the last three decades, the

research has been upgrading on electrode materials for achieving better features and to attain concentration by using the state-of-the-art of booming nanoscience and technology [6].

Although, Li-ion cells have become convenient, reliable and versatile for applications in several portable devices, extensive efforts are underway globally to extend the application of these batteries for electric mobility. These are anticipated to be useful for all emission-free vehicles. As global resources of Li are limited and their distribution is uneven on the earth, a large-scale production of Li-ion batteries is likely to be hampered. Alternate rechargeable batteries have received attention in recent years. The properties of Li vary gradually as their atomic mass increases [7- 9]. Anode and cathode of battery materials directly participate or indirectly help for catalytic action in an electrochemical conversion process. Even promote to get enhanced properties to achieve high capacity, high columbic efficiency and low toxicity, mainly to avoid unwanted additives.

Negative electrode is a premier part of LIBs. In 1980, Newman and Klemann¹⁴ firstly reported the highly reversible. Moreover, available negative nanoelectrodes had not been found for a long period of time. The conventional graphite- anode has failed in increasing the Li content in LiC_6 . Significant problems in operating at very low potential (< 0.1 V) and reversibility has become unsuccessful. For the past several years, great efforts have been made in the search for suitable anode materials [10, 11].

Nanomaterial electrodes for LIB possess following beneficial characteristics:

1. Shorter diffusion lengths for the Lithium-ion travelling from the particle core to the surface where it transfers to the electrolyte
2. Higher electrode-electrolyte contact area arising from the inherently high surface area which is a characteristic of the particles.

With the excessive growth in population and industrialization, the photocatalytic degradation of hazardous substances has been a very important technique to produce purified water for societal benignity. Industrial wastage is the aqueous discard results from the insoluble dyes (colorants) and pigments. For the complete degradation of insoluble dyes and recycling of catalyst is vital towards the pollution prevalence. Ozonization, chlorination and filtration have their own limits for the alleviation of dye degradation. Photocatalysis is green chemical pathway due to its environmental benignity, less energy consumable towards broad variety of technical and industrial applications. It enhances the rate of reaction in the presence of photocatalyst by producing hydroxyl radicals towards the termination of organic dyes [12, 13].

The quantitative determination of nitrite (NO_2^-) concentration is rapidly increasing interest, especially for drinking water quality, wastewater treatment, for the food industry and for the control of remediation procedures. Also, the control of water quality is important to avoid contamination of food produced when water is used as a raw material. Moreover, nitrites are routinely added to meat products as a preservative against food poisoning microorganisms such as *Clostridium botulinum* and continuously monitored because of their toxicity. Nitrites can be converted to carcinogenic nitroso amines in food products and within the human digestive system [14]. Electrochemical sensors have explored the attention for their low cost, portability and precision to control and monitor the toxic nitrites in the food and other industries. Electrochemical sensors are greatly miniaturised for nitrite detection. Few nitrite sensing oxide materials are exhibited lower detection limits due to fast electron transfer kinetics [15].

3. OBJECTIVES

- Synthesis of single/binary nanomaterials through hydrothermal, solvothermal, ionothermal, ionic liquid assisted, combustion or sonochemical method.
- Structural characterization of the above synthesized materials by X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), Raman spectroscopy, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), BET surface area, Thermo-gravimetric analysis (TGA), Optical properties by UV-vis spectroscopy, Photoluminescence spectroscopy and morphology by Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and Transmission electron microscopy (TEM).
- Investigation on the effect of temperature, precursor concentration, duration, surfactants, solvents etc. on the morphology of nanostructured materials.
- The above well-characterized single/binary nanomaterials, to be used as electrode material for lithium battery, as photocatalyst for dye degradation and as electrochemical nitrite sensing.

4. METHODOLOGY

Different methods available to prepare nanomaterials under solution chemistry routes are as follows. The synthesis of single/binary metal oxides, of functional nanomaterials with well controlled sizes, shapes, porosities, crystalline phases and structures include hydrothermal, solvothermal, sonochemical etc.

5. SUMMARY OF THE PROPOSED RESEARCH

In this study, synthesised the single/ binary compounds including Ta₂O₅, MoO₃, SnO₂-CuO and ZnWO₄-CuWO₄ advanced nanomaterials. The structural and morphology of the prepared nanomaterials are examined by XRD, FTIR, Raman spectroscopy, SEM and HRTEM. Thermal stability of the compounds is analysed by TGA-DTA analysis. Additional information such as surface area and band gap are obtained by BET and UV-DRS analysis. The electrochemical performance by various parameters like Charge-Discharge, Cyclic Voltammogram (CV) Columbic efficiency and Rate capability are studied towards lithium-ion batteries (LIBs). Photocatalysis includes the methylene blue (MB) dye degradation, this study has been carried out for the effluent's removal. Nitrite sensing gives the detection limit by using the glassy carbon electrode.

6. CHAPTER SCHEME

The thesis comprises seven chapters are as follows

Chapter 1 discusses the introduction of nanotechnology, nanomaterials classification and its properties, energy storage devices, mechanism of Li-ion batteries, photocatalytic dye degradation and nitrite sensing applications.

Chapter 2 describes the synthesis of nanomaterials using different methods and characterization using various analytical tools for spectroscopic and microscopic analysis.

Chapter 3 with the synthesis of Ta₂O₅ nanoparticles by sonochemical method. The high percentage of degradation of methylene blue (MB) dye is possible due to large surface area and a modest bandgap. Glassy carbon electrode (GCE) modified Ta₂O₅ NPs capable to detect 5 mM nitrite with lower detection limit.

Chapter 4 deals with the synthesis of h-MoO₃ hexagonal rods by reflux technique. The synthesized material was characterized by XRD, SEM and FTIR. The h-MoO₃ electrode has delivered outstanding discharge capacity at a current rate of C/15 over 100 cycles as well as maintained stability. Achieved lower detection limit by h-MoO₃ modified GCE.

Chapter 5 deals with the synthesis of SnO₂-CuO synthesis by sonochemical method. The prepared material was characterized by XRD, FTIR, SEM and TEM Techniques. The obtained binary composite SnO₂-CuO has been synthesized by sonochemical method. This

nanocomposite has delivered stable capacity even at higher 2C rate. SnO₂-CuO modified GCE has analysed for nitrite sensing and photocatalytic dye degradation.

Chapter 6 deals with the synthesis of ZnWO₄-CuWO₄ by combustion method using *Spondias mombin* (Hog plum) leaves as fuel towards the photocatalytic dye degradation and nitrite sensing.

Chapter 7 summarizes the results obtained in the present investigation and the scope for the future work.

7. SCOPE FOR THE FUTURE WORK

The lithium-ion battery concept can be extended to Li-air batteries, Li-S batteries, and even Na-ion batteries using novel electrode materials with various structures. The fabrication of graphene-based composites can further improve electrochemical performance. Photocatalytic dye degradation can be further continued to removal of industrial effluents with the binary/ternary composite photocatalysts. Nitrite sensing analysis can be adopted for the practical purpose with the utilization of various composites with carbon derivatives in order to increase the performance of the nitrite sensing.

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ABBREVIATIONS

a.c	Alternating Current
A g ⁻¹	Ampere per gram
BJH	Barrett-Joyner-Halenda
BET	Brunauer-Emmett-Teller Analysis
BOD	Biochemical oxygen demand
cm	Centimetre
R _{ct}	Charge transfer resistance
CV	Cyclic Voltammetry
CB	Conduction Band
COD	Chemical oxygen demand
DEC	Diethyl carbonate
DTA	Differential Thermal Analysis
DMC	Dimethyl carbonate
DRS	Diffuse Reflectance Spectroscopy
E	Energy density
EC	Ethylene carbonate
EG	Ethylene glycol
EDX	Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy
FE-SEM	Field Emission- Scanning Electron Microscopy
FT-IR	Fourier Transform Infra-Red Spectroscopy
FWHM	Full Width Half Maximum
Hz	Hertz
HR-TEM	High Resolution – Transmission Electron Microscopy
HEVs	Hybrid electric vehicles
KHz	Kilohertz
KBr	Potassium bromide
JCPDS	Joint committee on powder diffraction standards
Li ⁺	Lithium ion

LIB	Lithium-ion battery
MHz	Megahertz
mA h g ⁻¹	Milliamperere hour per gram
mM	Milli mole
mV	Milli volt
MB	Methylene Blue
nm	Nanometer
NMP	N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidinone
PHEVs	Plug-in-hybrid electric vehicles
PEG	Polyethylene glycol
PXRD	Powder X-ray Diffraction
PVA	Polyvinyl alcohol
PVDF	Poly(vinylidenedifluoride)
RhB	Rhodamine B
SEI	Solid electrolyte interface
SAED	Selected Area Electron Diffraction
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscope
UV-VIS	Ultra violet visible spectroscopy
VB	Valence Band
V	Voltage

SYMBOLS

α	Alpha
β	Beta
γ	Gamma
λ	Wavelength
θ	Theta
ν	Frequency
h	Planck's Constant
Kg	Kilogram
\AA	Angstrom
mg	Milligram
mL	Milliliter
$^{\circ}\text{C}$	Degree Celsius
eV	Electron Volts
Eg	Energy gap
a.u.	Arbitrary Units

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CHAPTER - I

Introduction

1.1 Nanotechnology

Nanotechnology pertains the study and application of tiny objects, applicable to all other scientific disciplines, including chemistry, biology, physics, materials science and engineering. In order to extrovert the nanotechnology, necessary to tune the functional materials to obtain the unique designs of significant physical, chemical, electrical and mechanical properties. The word 'nano' has been derived from the Greek word dwarf. One nanometer is one billionth of a meter [1-2]. Nanotechnology is existing since the evolution of earth, but the term is moderately acquainting to the scientific community. Poole and Owens book in 2003, mentioned that the abalone, a mollusc of the shell glued with carbohydrate-protein combination is the source of nano-bricks of calcium carbonate. Shells will be protected from the crack free resistance [3]. In earlies of 4th century, Romans using glassware's, made up of nano-sized metal salts. At 800 BC, Romans have made cup representing King Lycurgus death from silver and gold Nanoparticles (NPs), by the irradiation of light source, cup used to change it colours from green to red shown in **Figure 1.1**.

Figure 1.1 Lycurgus Cups

Ancient cathedral-stained windows also great example for the metallic NPs usage. Presence of peculiar colours in Maya fresco painting was due to the scattered gold NPs has concluded by Michel Faraday in 1857 [4]. Pioneering work of Gustav Mie showed that the small particles enough to vary the properties from bulk by the wide study of absorption and scattering of light by gold NPs [5]. *A. Magnetotactum* microorganisms are the witness of containing nanosized ferromagnetic particles i.e., Fe_3O_4 of 50 nm. Chinese used gold nanoparticles (NPs) as inorganic dye agents for ceramic porcelains for obtaining red colour in

around 1000 years ago [6, 7]. Seminar lecture by the Nobel prize winner Richard Feynman for Quantum Electrodynamics in the year 1959 stated that “There is Plenty of Room at the Bottom” in order to convey the significance of miniaturisation techniques [8, 9]. Development of integrated chips (ICs) has the major breakthrough in the field of nanotechnology, initially started with transistors of bulk macro-object in 1947. In the year 2002, booming nanotechnology come up with the single electron transistor around 90 nm range. Presently using Intel Core 2 Quad processors composed of 45 nm sized single electron transistor. Revolutionary invention of atomic force microscope (AFM) and scanning tunnelling microscope (STM) by Binnig and IBM Zurich co-workers impacted great on nanoscale surface imaging [10].

1.2 Nanomaterials

Nanomaterials comprised of atoms or molecules substituents termed as nanoparticles (NPs) are of 1 to 100 nm in any of the characteristic dimension. Nanomaterials are usually engineered in order to obtain the different unique structures by the different synthesis techniques, exhibits unique physical, chemical and mechanical properties. These materials are used in various applications including energy storage materials, water purification, electrochemical sensing, cosmetics, fabrication of microprocessor and in medical sector.

1.2.1 Classification of nanomaterials

Nanomaterials have been classified into four categories based on dimensions, these are 0D, 1D, 2D and 3D. Zero-dimensional nanomaterials don't have any dimensions. The electrons are confined in all the three directions and not allowed to move anywhere in the system. Examples includes nanospheres, quantum dots. In one-dimensional nanomaterials, electrons are confined in two directions and allowed to move in other one direction. 1D nanomaterials includes nanowires, nanotubes and nanorods. In two-dimensional nanomaterials, electrons are confined in one direction and free to move in other two directions. 2D nanomaterials include nano-thin films, nanosheets. In three-dimension materials, electrons are not confined and free to move all the three spatial directions. This class of materials are not considered as nanomaterials because in 3D materials, electrons are not confined in any of the dimension [11, 12]. 3D materials include dispersion of NPs, bulk powders, multi nanolayers/nanowires/nanotubes for example graphite. **Figure 1.2** portrays the classification of nanomaterials with examples.

Figure 1.2 Classification of nanomaterials with examples

1.2.2 Properties of nanomaterials

Fundamentally, properties of nanomaterials are different from the bulk particles. Nanomaterials with different dimensions, sizes and morphologies exhibits significant fascinating unique properties such as surface area, quantum confinement effect, magnetism, mechanical, thermal and electrical conductivity [13-15].

- **Surface area**

Surface area is very important parameter, nanomaterials exhibit high surface area compared to bulk material. NPs are extremely small that their surface to volume ratio is very high. Therefore, NPs exhibit relatively high surface area per unit mass compared to micro sized particles. Surface area of the NPs of porous, non-porous materials are quantified using BET (Nova Station 0) technique by the physical adsorption of N_2 gas at 77K.

- **Quantum confinement effect (QCE)**

Quantum confinement effect explores the electrons in terms of potential wells, energy levels, conduction bands, valence bands and electron energy band gaps. QCE is noticeable when the size of the particles is too small to be comparable with the wavelength of the light. Material properties alters significantly in the confinement of an electron and hole. Quantum tunnelling effect plays a major role in mobile touch screen. Hence such type of materials has

gained lot of attention due to their applications in light emitting devices, solar cells and biological labels.

- **Magnetism**

Magnetic effects in the functional nanomaterials differs compared to bulk state of materials. The atomic scale magnetic moment, magnetic order occurrence and magnetic moments alignment in the appropriate crystallographic axis contribute towards magnetic anisotropy. These magnetic nanomaterials have tremendous applications towards magnetic recording, telecommunications, biology and actuators.

- **Thermal and electrical conductivity**

Thermal conductivity of nanomaterials offers the unique electrical properties. These materials capable to provide great strength and efficiency. These properties are most suitable in electronics, medicine, optics and architecture domains. Thermochromic materials are used in thermometers.

- **Mechanical properties**

Mechanical properties such as strength, melting point exhibits drastic variation at nanoscale. Nanomaterials are harder, stronger, wear-resistant, corrosion resistant, fracture toughness, fracture strength and ultimate tensile strength. These smart materials (shape memory alloys) are extensively used in automobile industry. Piezoelectric materials are used in sensors.

1.3 Electrochemical energy storage and conversion systems

Global ecology and economics impacted greatly by the combustion of fossil fuels for the energy consumption or production. Main goal for achieving the global energy sustainability rely on replacing the fossil fuels such as oils, coal, natural gas with renewable energies such as geothermal, biomass, hydrogen, batteries etc. More consumption of fossil fuels impacts greatly on the environment change. It is hazardous to all living creatures on the earth's crust. Renewable energy sources are unpredictable, costs high for the conversion and distribution. **Figure 1.3** gives the statistics reported by International Energy Agency (IEA).

As an alternative power/energy source, electrochemical energy storage systems are in serious consideration, due to the zero emissive, more sustainable and environmental

benignity. Electrochemical energy storage and conversion systems includes batteries, fuel cells and super capacitors, all these undergo different storage and conversion mechanisms.

Figure 1.3 Total energy supply by fuel (in %), Source: IEA, World Balances, 2021

A comprehensive chart to evaluate the performance of energy storage devices is through Ragone plot as shown in **Figure 1.4**. In this specific power density is plotted against the energy density of common energy storage systems. It is easily understandable that Li-ion batteries have utilized vastly for the wide range of applications. Batteries are falls under high energy density criteria [16].

Figure 1.4 Ragone plot of usual energy storage systems

All the three systems provide energy at the phase boundary means electrode-electrolyte interface. Batteries and fuel cells comprised of two electrodes in contact with

electrolytic solution for the electrons and the ion conductivity. Generation of electrical energy from the chemical energy through the redox reactions at the electrodes. Reactions of lower electrode potentials usually occurs at anodes compared to cathode. Location of the energy storage and conversion matters for the differentiation of batteries and fuel cells. Charge-transfer medium takes place in the closed system means same compartment for energy storage as well as conversion are batteries. Fuel cells are of open systems for the charge transfer media through anode and cathode. Fuel cells converts energy with the continuous fuel supply such as hydrogen, oxygen and hydrocarbon. Supercapacitors make utilize of electrical double layers will plays a major role i.e., electrolyte interface means movement of electrons in the external device. Fuel cells and supercapacitors developed to replace many of the battery sector. Fuel cells are high energy and supercapacitors are high power systems [17].

1.3.1 Timeline of the major events in the history of batteries

More than 2000 years ago, Egyptians most likely employed rechargeable batteries in battery-like devices to electroplate gold onto silver now referred as Baghdad batteries. Contrarily, the history of batteries has only been documented in writing since the late 1700s and early 1800s [18]. The key developments in battery technology from 1791 are shown in **Figure 1.5**.

Figure 1.5 Timeline of major events during evolution of batteries

Galvani (1791) demonstrated that animal tissues may produce bioelectric current. Volta (1800) made the discovery of the Voltaic piles as a result of the experiment. In 1836, Daniel created the Daniel cell, a long-lasting battery. The lead-acid battery was presented by Gaston Plante to the French Academy of Science in 1859 [19]. Since then, several main, secondary and tertiary electrochemical energy storage devices were developed. The inadequate energy densities and capacities of existing batteries had led to a search for new battery chemistries by the 20th century, and lithium had emerged as a leading candidate. The lightest metal is lithium, which has an atomic number of 3 and a density of 0.53 g cm⁻³. It is a great option for high-density and high-voltage batteries. The LIBs basis was laid during the oil crises of the 1970s. Stanley Whittingham concentrated on ways to advance technologies for fossil fuel free energy. He started researching on superconductors and discovered a remarkable energy-dense titanium disulphide, that could hold lithium ions, which he utilised to create a ground-breaking cathode. The battery's anode is made of metallic lithium, which has a strong propensity for releasing electrons. As a result, the battery had a lot of potential at a voltage of slightly above 2 V. On the other hand, metallic lithium is reactive, making the battery unsafe to use.

According to John Goodenough, using metal oxide instead of metal sulphide for the cathode would be far more promising. This ground-breaking alteration to the LIBs cathode has revolutionised a powerful battery that was once seen as promising. Akira Yoshino created the first commercially practical lithium-ion battery in 1985 by employing petroleum coke as an anode instead of lithium metal to intercalate lithium ions. The cathode was made up of lithium cobalt oxide. The outcome was a durable, light-weight battery with an infinite capacity that could be recharged hundreds of times. At 1991 Sony Company released lithium-ion batteries for commercial use, drastically altered our lives. John B. Goodenough, M. Stanley Whittingham and Akira Yoshino have been awarded the 2019 Nobel Prize in Chemistry for their revolutionary work on LIBs.

1.3.2 Basics of batteries

Batteries are electrochemical devices that converts chemical energy of the active materials into electrical energy. Battery comprised of a cell or group of electrochemical cells connected serial or parallel or both ways depending on the desired capacity and voltage output. Batteries are worldwide used sources of direct current electrical energy automobiles,

boats, ships, portable electric/electronic equipment and lighting equipment along with secondary or standby power source. Block diagram of the battery is as shown in **Figure 1.6**.

Figure 1.6 Block diagram of battery

1.3.3 Components of the batteries

The basic building blocks of all the batteries are

- Anode electrode
- Cathode electrode
- Electrolyte
- Separator
- Container

1.3.3.1 Anode electrode

The anode is negative electrode in an electrochemical cell. During the discharging operation, the negative electrode gives up ions towards cathode for an oxidation chemical reaction. During charging process, anode accepts the ions from cathode for the reduction process. Redox reactions occur simultaneously. Electrons will flow in an external circuit from anode to cathode during discharging and cathode to anode during the charging process. Materials with very few electrons in their valence shell, either metals or metals combined elements suitable for anodes. Anode materials should act as efficient reducing agent, high coulombic output, good conductivity, stable, ease of fabrication and cost effective.

1.3.3.2 Cathode electrode

The cathode is positive electrode in an electrochemical cell. During the discharging operation, the positive electrode accepts the ions from anode towards reduction chemical reaction and undergoes oxidation reaction i.e., cathode releases ions towards anode during charging process. Redox reactions occur simultaneously. Electrons will flow in an external circuit from cathode to anode during charging and anode to cathode in the discharging process. Materials of nearly filled valence shells are most suitable for cathode materials mainly metal oxides are most promising cathode electrode materials. The cathode materials must be very stable when in contact with the electrolyte. Cathode materials should act as efficient oxidizing agent, useful operating voltage, ease of fabrication and of low cost.

1.3.3.3 Electrolyte

An electrolyte come up with the good ionic conductivity among the electrodes. During the electron's movement in the external circuit, same time ions move in the opposite direction between the electrodes and acts as channel to transfer ions as charge. Newly obtained ions must be pass between the electrodes through electrolyte in order to sustain the flow of electrons. Electrolytes have certain characteristics including strong ionic conductivity, no electric conductivity, non-reactivity with electrode materials, resistance to temperature fluctuations, handling safety. Typically, electrolytes are liquids for example water or any other solvents with the dissolution of salts, acids, or alkalis to proclaim ionic conductivity.

1.3.3.4 Separator

A separator/membrane is a physical barrier placed in between the electrodes to avoid electrical shorting. Separator is a micro porous polymeric film or gelled electrolyte, or other porous inert material filled with electrolyte. Separators are mainly permeable to the ions and inert in the battery environment.

1.3.3.5 Container

The container is constructed to mount the electrodes and separator. Helps to hold the electrolyte. Container is made up of one or many materials. The materials of the container should not react with electrolyte.

1.3.4 Types of batteries

Basically, two types of batteries are available

- Primary batteries
- Secondary batteries

1.3.4.1 Primary batteries

Primary batteries are assembled in a charged state and discharging happens during the way that electrical energy could be used until the exhaustion and later discarded. During discharging chemical compounds will be permanently altered. Thus, the battery can be used only once.

1.3.4.2 Secondary batteries

Secondary batteries are reversible include the recharging option, can be restored after the cell was discharged. Therefore, secondary batteries are also termed as rechargeable batteries or accumulators. These are acts as galvanic cells during the discharging and electrolytic cell during charging. There are several rechargeable batteries i.e., metal-ion batteries including lithium-ion [20], sodium-ion [21], aluminium-ion [22], zinc-ion [23], magnesium-ion [24], potassium-ion [25]. Advanced metal-air batteries include lithium-air, zinc-air, magnesium-air, aluminium-air [26] and hydrogen batteries are in the present trend [27].

Here below discussed few main secondary batteries from which LIBs are evolved.

- Nickel-Cadmium battery
- Nickel-Metal Hydride battery
- Lead acid battery
- Li-ion battery

1.3.4.3 Nickel-Cadmium battery (Ni-Cd)-Nickel-Cadmium battery composed of nickel oxyhydroxide (NiOOH) along with a combination of 5 % Co(OH)_2 , Ba(OH)_2 and 20 % graphite for a cathode and cadmium (Cd) as anode along with 25 % iron and other small quantities of nickel and graphite to prevent agglomeration. Ni-Cd battery gives long life, high discharge rate and economical. In two-way radios, video cameras and biomedical equipment

Disadvantages

- Memory effect
- Relatively low energy density

- Has relatively high self-discharge
- Environmentally unfriendly

1.3.4.4 Nickel-Metal Hydride (NiMH) battery: This battery is capable to deliver higher energy density compared Ni-Cd battery but reduced cyclic life and expensive. NiMH battery composed of non-toxic elements and used in laptop computers and cell phones.

Disadvantages

- High self-discharge
- Limited-service life
- About 20 percent more expensive than Ni-Cd
- Performance degrades if stored at elevated temperatures

1.3.4.5 Lead acid battery: Lead acid battery consists of lead (Pb) metal as anode and lead dioxide (PbO₂) as cathode. Electrodes are dipped in electrolyte of H₂SO₄. Electrodes are turned into lead sulphate and electrolyte will be consumed during the process. Large scale applications prefer this lead-acid battery due to less cost. These batteries are most suitable for hospital equipment, emergency lighting, wheelchairs and UPS systems.

Disadvantages

- Allows only a limited number of full discharge cycles
- Transportation restrictions on flooded lead acid
- Environmentally unfriendly
- Low energy and power density

1.4 Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs)

Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) are popularized worldwide as power sources for electric gadgets and electric vehicles (EVs). LIBs have found usage by its memory protection in several electronic devices and for the instantaneous power backup systems. Due to the booming applications, batteries have been commercialized due to the requirement of high-power devices. LIBs have capable to deliver the three times higher theoretical capacity than lead acid or Ni-Cd for the same size and weight and two times higher than NiMH battery. Due to the characteristics of lithium, LIBs have become enabler for the electronics revolution. LIBs operate over -20 to +50 °C operating temperature and charge-discharge cycles may go more than thousands. To evaluate the energy contents in the system, specific energy density (mA h g⁻¹). **Table 1.1** explains the properties of lithium.

Table 1.1 Properties of lithium	
Category	Lithium (Li)
Atomic number	3
Relative atomic mass	6.94
Melting point (°C)	180.5
Boiling point (°C)	1347
Density (g/cc)	0.53
E° vs. SHE (V)	-3.04
Atomic radius (pm)	157
First ionization energy (kJ mol ⁻¹)	520.2
Abundance in sea water (ppm)	0.2
Abundance in the earth crust (%)	0.008
Cost (\$/ton)	15,000
Theoretical capacity (mA h g ⁻¹)	3861

1.4.1 Working principle of LIBs

Lithium ions insertion-extraction during discharging-charging process from the interstitial space between atomic layers of the active material towards Li metal and vice-versa in the battery process. **Figure 1.7** explains the schematic illustration of traversing Li-ions among the electrodes via electrolyte to the metal matrix.

Figure 1.7 Schematic illustration of lithium-ion battery

1.4.2 Properties of electrode materials for LIBs

The insertion compound employed as an electrode should have a sufficient lithium potential to increase the cell voltage. With the minimal or no structural changes in the electrode material feasible for the reversible Li-ion insertion and extraction. Accessible to the quick charge-discharge process in-turns at the high rate. Ohmic resistance should be lower to achieve the electrical conductivity for the good specific capacity and reversibility. To improve the conductivity, additional conductive carbon is preferred. Electrode materials should not react with an electrolyte and should be chemically stable throughout the working voltage range. Electrode materials should have non-toxicity, safe and environmentally benign, high thermal stability and deliver less heat. The procedure for synthesising an electrode material should be simple and flexible to maintain costs as low as possible. An excellent electrode material needs to be quick to recharge, have low-capacity fading, and have a high cycle life. From a commercial standpoint, the substance should be easily accessible, cheap and abundant in nature.

Numerous substances have been investigated for the electrodes, including halides, chalcogens, polyanionic compounds [24], conducting polymers [25] and their composites with oxides [26], layered oxide [27], spinel oxides [28] and olivine's [29]. Based on the key characteristics of lithium ion mentioned above, materials have been prepared as electrodes for batteries. Sulphides, phosphides, oxides and sulphides of transition metals carbonaceous and non-carbonaceous materials, as well as nitrides materials, all materials that are employed as anodes [30]. This thesis includes the advanced single/binary nanomaterials as electrode materials towards LIBs.

There are three types of lithium-ions intercalation-deintercalation mechanism with the electrode materials shown in **Figure 1.8**.

- Insertion-extraction mechanism
- Alloying-de-alloying mechanism
- Conversion reaction mechanism

Insertion-extraction mechanism: Usually 2D layered or 3D network structures of transition metal oxides and other compounds undergoes this mechanism. It is a reversible reaction mechanism. Li-ions intercalates into the lattice (like graphite) without destroying the crystal structure, therefore this type of reaction mechanism exhibits relatively low theoretical capacity.

Figure 1.8 Electrochemical reaction mechanism of LIBs

Alloying-dealloying mechanism: In this type, compounds adopt distinct crystal structure and different physical properties compared to Li or electrode materials. Alloying-dealloying reaction mechanism occurs at lower potential (≤ 1.0 V vs. Li). This mechanism delivers higher theoretical capacity.

Conversion reaction mechanism: In this type, redox or conversion reactions occurred in between the electrode materials and Li metal with the formation of Li_2O and respective elements. Electrochemically inactive Li_2O cannot decomposed into Li metal and oxygen. Usually oxides, sulphides, fluorides, nitrides undergo conversion reaction mechanism. This mechanism exhibits lower theoretical capacity than alloying-dealloying reaction mechanism and higher than insertion/extraction mechanism [28].

1.5 Photocatalytic activity: Dye degradation

Degradation of toxic chemicals has become a very essential approach for societal benignity because of rapid increasing of textile industries. Industrial insoluble dyes (colourants) and pigments are very hazardous towards human beings and aquatic life. The complete breakdown of insoluble dyes and the recycling of catalyst are critical for reducing the pollution. Dyes are of several types including organic/inorganic, natural/synthetic, chemical makeup and dyeing method, in that Methylene Blue (MB), tartrazine, Congo Red

(CR), Indigo Carmine (IC), Rhodamine B (Rb) and other artificial dyes are carcinogenic and mutagenic dyes [29].

1.5.1 Types of wastewater treatment

1.5.1.1 Primary wastewater treatment

This method extracted from a variety of materials, including rocks, horns, fibres, and bottles. Debris and big materials are usually removed in this procedure. Searching, inspection, accumulation, concentration, gravity separation, coagulation and other methods are used in this procedure [30].

1.5.1.2 Secondary wastewater treatment

Removal of phenol, oil, BOD and COD contents in the contaminated water will be taking place in secondary wastewater treatment [31].

1.5.1.3 Tertiary wastewater treatment

This method involves the removal of phosphates and nitrates from the contaminated water. Activated carbon and sand are the main supporting materials used in this method. Cleaning methods of primary and secondary wastewater treating methods are not sufficient. Removal of textile effluents means of organic dyes is crucial to put efforts on research. Aforementioned methods had failed to remove the organic molecules such as azo dyes. Besides, conventional methods extract the harmful products which are mutagenic and carcinogenic and limited for phase transformation of organic molecules and impact for sludge production. In this way, many methods are expensive and maintenance is also difficult. Therefore, researchers have come up with many cost-effective and environmental benign methods. Nanoparticles (NPs) have exhibited enhanced results in an advanced oxidation process method [32].

1.5.1.4 Advanced oxidation process

This is one of the wastewater treating method for organic and inorganic molecules in hydroperoxyl radicals based on the generation of $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals. Highly reactive hydroxyl radicals include the Fenton process. In this method strongest oxidants of O_2 , H_2O_2 will be produced by light interaction using nanocatalysts of TiO_2 , ZnO , CdS , WO_3 , Fe_2O_3 etc., [33-

35]. Organic species are easily oxidized in the water matrix. Under this process there are four different methods to remove the organic molecules.

- (i) Ozone treatment
- (ii) Electrochemical process
- (iii) Direct degradation
- (iv) Photocatalysis

(i) Ozone treatment: In this technique, ozone gas can be directly utilised into harmful water, where it reacts with organic molecules that contain $\cdot\text{OH}$ species, resulting in indirect oxidative dissociation. Ozone pollution is a key component for promoting or preventing ozone depletion. As a result, in the presence of ozone, unsaturated organic contents are difficult to breakdown [36].

(ii) Electrochemical process: When exposed to light, water molecules convert into H^+ , electrons and $\cdot\text{OH}$. Heat produces, when increasing the greater voltage pulses of > 10 kV are discharged into water through two electrodes superimposed, which aids in the disintegration of water molecules. External energy sources produce a similar scenario in which hot patches are formed above heated regions. Most voltage pulses (> 10 kV) are delivered into water through two electrodes when water molecules are broken into H^+ , electrons and $\cdot\text{OH}$, though liberates local heat, which helps to break the water molecules. External energy sources provided through the generation of hot areas by the similar state.

(iii) Direct decomposition: In this direct decomposition method, decomposition of H_2O_2 forms $\cdot\text{OH}$ by Fenton in iron salt's reaction upon light illumination [37]. Technique was invented by Fenton in 1894. This is more interestingly explored by advancement in the conventional wastewater treatment.

In this equation, iron salts further advanced in the breakdown of organic compounds. The main disadvantage of this approach is, it is ineffective at pH-4; therefore, modified pH should be employed, which may increase operating costs and H_2O_2 is easier for maintaining. This process is also healthy for the environment since it occurred earlier in the splitting of organic molecules.

(iv) Photocatalysis: Photocatalytic activity is green chemical pathway for the sustainable ecological system and uses less energy in a wide range of wavelength. It is very promising towards environmental and energy concerns used mainly in degradation of toxic organic pollutants and water splitting for hydrogen generation. Photocatalysis is a phenomenon that uses photon energy to accelerate a reaction in the presence of a catalyst by creating hydroxyl radicals that help to terminate organic dyes. Commercial applications due to their colour flexibility and improved long-term stability [38].

Semiconductor photocatalysts are considered as promising materials for the degradation of dye effluents, because of its unique physio-chemical properties. High photosensitivity could be achievable by increasing the charge separation in a photo-responding range of wide band gap. Heterogeneous photocatalysts provides many advantages, including (i) the light absorption capacity by combining metal/non-metal, other semiconductors and noble metals and (ii) metal with semiconductor heterostructures improves the charge separation rate by enabling the Schottky junction (iii) combining with other co-catalyst could lower the redox potential [39].

1.5.2 Mechanism of photocatalytic dye degradation

Schematic illustration of semiconductor photocatalysis mechanism is as shown in **Figure 1.9**. When this semiconductor photocatalyst is irradiated with photons energy of equivalent or greater than their band gap energy. Once after receiving the sufficient energy, electrons are stimulated to the conduction band (CB) from the valence band (VB).

Positive holes will be leaving behind. By avoiding the recombination, can improve the migration of the excited electrons and generated holes to the surface of photocatalyst through the redox reactions.

Formation of peroxides and superoxides by the reduction of oxygen through the excited electrons. Hydroxyl radicals are produced by the oxidation of water through the holes. The generated radicals are very reactive and unstable, resulting in the degradation of dye molecules and by releasing the by-products such as H_2O_2 , CO_2 and so on [40-42].

Figure 1.9 Mechanism of photocatalytic dye

1.6 Electrochemical nitrite sensing

Nitrite (NO_2^-) is a toxic contaminant that is widely utilised in agriculture and food industry as preservatives, therefore commonly found in drinking water and food. Over usage of nitrite may lead to severe diseases. Many nitrite detecting techniques have been proposed, however electrochemical sensor have gained popularity due to their high precision sensitivity, cost-effectiveness and reliability [43]. Modified glassy carbon electrode (GCE) have numerous advantages over traditional graphite and carbon paste electrodes. GCE provides good sensitivity and selectivity. Electrochemical redox reactions of nitrite with molecular oxygen on the surface of electrode is the key point to detect nitrite. Reacted intermediate elements absorbed by surface of GCE [44]. **Figure 1.10** shows the mechanism of electrochemical nitrite sensing.

Figure 1.10 Mechanism of nitrite sensing

Transition metal oxides have capable to exhibit superior electro-catalytic results due to the feasible oxygen adsorption and electron transfer activity between the active species. Unique structure, wide band gap and high surface area, of the electrocatalytic nanomaterials helps to develop chemical inertness to moisture and oxygen for the detection of nitrite [45].

1.7 Literature survey

This section discusses the elaborated background of the research title is widely reviewed. Exploring the advanced nanomaterials for the viable electrodes for LIBs, photocatalytic dye degradation and nitrite sensing for the societal consideration in terms of energy storage, pollution control and well-being of the living creatures across the world along with the scope of the present investigation. **Table 1.2** summarises the advanced transition metal oxide materials for LIBs, photocatalytic dye degradation and nitrite sensing applications.

Table 1.2 Detailed review of the advanced nanomaterials for lithium- ion battery, photocatalytic dye degradation and nitrite sensing				
Compounds	Synthesis	Structural characterization	Applications and Results	References
Mesoporous Ta ₂ O ₅ NPs	Hydrothermal	XRD, FTIR, Raman, TG-DTA, DRS, BET, SEM, TEM	150 mA h g ⁻¹ specific capacity even after 50 cycles at the 0.1 C rate	[46]
Ta ₂ O ₅ film	Reactive pulsed laser deposition	XRD, SEM, TEM, XPS	411 mA h g ⁻¹ specific capacity even after 100 cycles at 20 μA/cm ²	[47]
Ta ₂ O ₅ aerogel	Sol gel	XRD, BET, SEM, TEM, XPS	205 mA h g ⁻¹ specific capacity even after 8000 cycles at 5C current rate	[48]
Ta ₂ O ₅ NPs	Hydrothermal	XRD, BET, SEM, TEM	130 mA h g ⁻¹ specific capacity even after 85 cycles @ 0.1C	[49]
h-MoO ₃ nanorods	Chemical mixing method	XRD, FTIR, SEM, TEM, XPS	780 mA h g ⁻¹ specific capacity after 150 cycles @ 150 mA g ⁻¹	[50]
MoO _{3-x} nanowire array	Chemical vapour deposition method	XRD, Raman, SEM, TEM	590 mA h g ⁻¹ specific capacity even after 20 cycles @ 100 mA g ⁻¹	[51]
MoO ₃ porous film	Hydrothermal	XRD, Raman, SEM, TEM	450 mA h g ⁻¹ specific capacity even after 50 cycles @ 1C rate	[52]
α-MoO ₃ nanoflowers	Sonochemical	XRD, Raman, SEM, TEM	810.7 mA h g ⁻¹ specific capacity even after 100 cycles @ 0.1 C	[53]

V ₂ O ₅ nanowire clusters	Gel-combustion	XRD, FTIR, SEM, TEM	Exhibited 188 mA h g ⁻¹ specific capacity at 50 th cycle at 60 mA g ⁻¹ current density	[54]
V ₂ O ₅ NPs	Combustion	XRD, FESEM	320 mA h g ⁻¹ specific capacity after 50 cycles at 0.1 C	[55]
V ₂ O ₅ crusts	Combustion	XRD, SEM, TEM	210 mA h g ⁻¹ specific capacity after 30 cycles at 0.1 C rate	[56]
SnO ₂ -CuO nanotubes	Electrospinning	XRD, TGA, BET, FESEM, TEM, XPS	538 mA h g ⁻¹ specific capacity even after 350 cycles at 500 mA g ⁻¹ current density	[57]
CuO/SnO ₂ nanocomposite	Facile thermal annealing	XRD, Raman, FESEM, TEM	718 mA h g ⁻¹ specific capacity even after 200 cycles at 500 mA g ⁻¹ current density	[58]
SnO ₂ -CuO nanocomposite	Co-precipitation	XRD, TG-DTA, SEM	752 mA h g ⁻¹ specific capacity even after 60 cycles at the rate of 0.1 C	[59]
CuO@SnO ₂ nanobelts	Hydrothermal	XRD, SEM, TEM	584.3 mA h g ⁻¹ specific capacity even after 100 cycles at 100 mA g ⁻¹	[60]
ZnWO ₄	Co-precipitation	XRD, FTIR, SEM, TEM	Photocatalytic degradation of 81 % MB dye in UV	[61]
CuWO ₄	Solvothermal	XRD, FTIR, UV-DRS, BET, SEM	Photocatalytic degradation of 86 % MB dye after 90 min under UV-vis light. irradiation	[62]
ZnWO ₄	Sol-gel	XRD, FTIR, DRS, BET, FESEM, TEM	Degradation of MB dye in UV irradiation, rate constant $k = 1.62 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$	[63]
Ta ₂ O ₅ NPs	Mechanical milling and calcination	XRD, Raman, BET, FE-SEM, TEM	Degradation of 81 % of within 180 min MB dye in UV-vis irradiation	[64]
CdFe ₂ O ₄ NPs	Combustion method	XRD, FTIR, Raman, BET, UV_DRS, SEM, TEM	Degradation of 96 % MB dye under visible light	[65]
SnO ₂ /CuO nanocomposite	Chemical method	XRD, FTIR, SEM, TEM,	Achieved 92 % of MB dye degradation in 30 min under visible light	[66]
ZnFe ₂ O ₄	Combustion	XRD, FTIR, Raman, BET, UV-DRS, SEM	Degradation of 98 % of Rhodamine B under visible light	[67]
ZnO	Solution phase approach	XRD, UV-DRS, FESEM, TEM	Degradation of 95% within 70 min for the Rhodamine B dye under UV light	[68]

Fe ₂ O ₃ /rGO	Hydrothermal	XRD, FESEM	Detection limit of 0.015 x 10 ⁻⁶ M for the concentration range of 5.0 × 10 ⁻⁸ to 7.8 × 10 ⁻⁴ M	[69]
Co ₃ O ₄ /rGO	Thermal decomposition	XRD, Raman, BET, SEM, TEM, XPS	Detection of 0.14 μM for the concentration of 1–380 M for nitrite	[70]
ZnO ₂ /rGO	Hydrothermal	XRD, Raman, FESEM, TEM	Detection limit of 33 μM concentration of nitrite in the 10 μM to 8 mM range nitrite in the 10 μM to 8 mM range	[71]
Fe ₂ O ₃ polyhedrons	Facile solution route	XRD, SEM, TEM	Detection of nitrite in the range between 0.009 and 3 mM of sensitivity 19.83 μA/mM ⁻¹	[72]
CoO _x	Surface modification using GCE	SEM, CV (amperometry method)	Detection limit and sensitivity towards nitrite are 0.20 μM and 10.5 nA/μM respectively	[73]

1.3 Brief Summary

In this study, advanced single/binary compounds have been synthesised using different wet-chemical routes. The structural and morphology of the prepared nanomaterials are examined by XRD, FTIR, Raman spectroscopy, SEM and HRTEM. Thermal stability of the compounds has analysed by TGA-DTA analysis. Additional information such as surface area and band gap are obtained by BET and UV-DRS analysis. Confirmed nanomaterials have used for the studies of (i) Li-ion battery (ii) Photocatalytic dye degradation (iii) Electrochemical nitrite sensing.

(i) To obtain high electrochemical performance in terms of high discharge capacity and high-rate capability, Charge-Discharge, Cyclic Voltammogram (CV), Columbic efficiency and Rate capability towards lithium-ion batteries (LIBs). Advanced nanomaterials of single/binary nanomaterials of Ta₂O₅, MoO₃ and SnO₂-CuO are prepared using different synthesis routes and studied the electrochemical performance.

(ii) Photocatalytic dye degradation of single/binary compounds of various size and shape are considered for the MB dye degradation. Advanced nanomaterials of Ta₂O₅, SnO₂-CuO and ZnWO₄-CuWO₄ are explored for photocatalytic studies. This includes the in-depth analysis includes experiments by varying the catalyst dosage, dye concentration and different pH levels for the effluent's removal.

(iii) Nitrite sensing using advanced single/binary nanomaterials have explored using Ta₂O₅, MoO₃ and SnO₂-CuO and ZnWO₄-CuWO₄ nanomaterials using glassy carbon electrode (GCE) for measuring the detection limit.

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CHAPTER - II

Experimental methods and Characterization Techniques

This chapter describes the preparation of nanoparticles (NPs) and the techniques for the characterization. The basic aspects of the thesis include the experimental methodologies to obtain the different nanomaterials of various structural analysis towards Li-ion battery, photocatalytic dye degradation and nitrite sensing. Briefly explored the basics of spectroscopic and microscopic techniques used to examine the prepared nanomaterials.

2.1 Synthesis methods of nanoparticles

Synthesis of nanomaterials is broadly categorized into top-down and bottom-up approaches. Top-down technique uses chemical, mechanical or other sources of energy for the formation of nanoparticles. Electron beam lithography [1], aerosol spray [2], gas-phase condensation [3] and ball milling [4] are some of the techniques that fall under the top-down approach. Bottom-up strategy based on atomic or molecular species that include hydrothermal [5], co-precipitation [6], ultrasonication [7], sol-gel [8], electrodeposition [9] and combustion [10] methods. Bottom-up approach is most preferable for the nanomaterials preparation because it is capable to achieve uniform chemical composition, defect-free nanostructures, less time consuming and simple procedures for the preparation and are cost-effective. **Figure 2.1** explains the advantages and disadvantages of top down and bottom-up approaches.

Figure 2.1 Advantages and disadvantages of top-down and bottom-up approaches

Here, discussed few wet-chemical bottom-up methods of synthesis for single/ binary nanomaterials.

2.1.1 Hydrothermal synthesis

For the preparation NPs of desired shape and size, hydrothermal method has been considered. Teflon lined air-tight autoclave acts as hydrothermal bomb to maintain the pressure. Hydrothermal method offers low cost, preparable with easily available raw materials and simple procedure. In solvothermal, different solvents with different physical and chemical characteristics can affect the solubility, reactivity and diffusion behaviour of the reactants; in particular, the solvent's polarity and coordinating capability can affect the final products shape and crystallisation behaviour. Ionic liquid is employed as a co-solvent together with water or an organic solvent in the ionothermal process, which also involves heat treatment [11].

2.1.2 Sonochemical method

Sonochemical method is very effective method for obtaining the uniform distribution of the particles through the ultrasonic radiation. In this method, precursors solution will be sonicated to carry out the ultrasonication. During the reaction, the atoms will diffuse into the bubbles by ultrasonic radiation of 20 KHz-10 MH, undergoes mechanical agitation in liquid solution. Nucleation and diffusion of the molecules as in terms causes the breakage of chemical bonds takes place in the sonicator (Ultrasonic homogenizer UZ SONOPULS HD 2070) using the ultrasonic radiation of frequency ranges from 20 KHz to 10 MHz. The solute atoms will diffuse into the bubbles, causing the growth; in the meantime, the bubbles will be mechanically agitated in liquid solution. During the collapse time less than 1 ns, as per the cooling and temperature rate, it's of extremely high ($5000\text{--}25,000\text{ K} > 10^{11}\text{ K/s}$), in order to break chemical bonds [12].

2.1.3 Combustion method

Combustion method is a single step technique and easy procedure for the preparation of metal oxide NPs. This method is cost effective, less time-consuming and helps for the creation of porosity in the structure. Usually, combustion method prefers for the bulk scale production of NPs. Combustion method involves generating the NPs by applying appropriate temperature to the specific quantity of oxidizer and fuel for the exothermic reactions. Now a days preparation of metal oxides using green fuels also trending. Synthesis of NPs usually undergo solution combustion method (SCS) [13]. **Figure 2.2** explains the advantages and disadvantage of various synthesis methods.

2.1.4 Sol-gel method

Sol-gel method of synthesising achieves nanosized particles with the optimised conditions to control the particles growth. Sol-gel method is cost effective, more effective, less toxicity. Sol-gel method greatly impact to engineer the surface morphology. Establishing the inorganic network through colloidal suspension (sol) and gelation to obtain gel network will takes place.

Figure 2.2 Advantages and disadvantages of different wet-chemical routes

2.2 Materials used

This research includes many chemicals to carry out the experiments, that are listed below along with the supplier details.

Materials	Formula	Supplier	Purity
Tantalum (V) chloride	TaCl ₅	Merck (India)	99.9 %
Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO)	(CH ₃) ₂ SO	Sigma Aldrich (India)	99.9 %
Absolute ethanol	C ₂ H ₅ OH	Sigma Aldrich (India)	99.0 %
Ammonium heptamolybdate	(NH ₄) ₆ Mo ₇ O ₂₄	SD Fine Chem (India)	99.0 %
Urea	CH ₄ N ₂ O	SD Fine Chem (India)	99.0 %
Tin (II) chloride dihydrate	SnCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	SD Fine Chem (India)	99.0 %

Copper (II) nitrate trihydrate	$\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	SD Fine Chem (India)	99.0 %
Sodium hydroxide	NaOH	SD Fine Chem (India)	99.0 %
Zinc nitrate hexahydrate	$\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Merck (India)	99.0 %
Tungstic acid	H_2WO_4	Merck (India)	99.0 %
Hydrochloric acid	HCl	Merck (India)	99.0 %
Nitric acid	HNO_3	Merck (India)	99.0 %
Sulphuric acid	H_2SO_4	Merck (India)	98.0 %
carbon black	C	Sigma Aldrich (India)	99.9 %
Lithium Foil	Li	Sigma Aldrich (India)	99.9 %
polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF)	$(\text{CH}_2\text{CF}_2)_n$	Sigma Aldrich (India)	99.0 %
N-methyl pyrrolidinone (NMP)	$\text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{NO}$	Sigma Aldrich (India)	99.0 %
Lithium-ion battery electrolyte	1 M LiPF_6 in ethylene carbonate (EC), diethyl carbonate (DEC) and dimethyl carbonate (DMC) (2:2:1)	Sigma Aldrich (India)	99.9 %
Methylene blue (MB)	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{18}\text{ClN}_3\text{S}$	Alfa Aesar (India)	99.9 %
Methyle orange (MO)	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_3\text{NaO}_3\text{S}$	Alfa Aesar (India)	99.9 %

2.3 Characterization Techniques

The following characterisation techniques have been used to investigate the crystal formation, phase structure, thermal stability, surface area, size, morphology of the single/binary nanomaterials.

2.3.1 Powder X-Ray diffraction (PXRD)

The crystallinity and phase structure of the synthesised samples were analysed by powder X-Ray diffraction. when X-Ray beam of wavelength (λ) is directed onto a crystalline material at an angle θ , diffraction occurs only when the rays reflected from successive planes differs by an integral n , lattice spacing is d and by satisfying Bragg's equation.

$$2d \sin\theta = n\lambda \quad (2.1)$$

The average crystallite size is determined by the breadth of the diffraction peaks in a specific pattern. Sharp peaks result from large crystallites, but peak breadth increases as crystallite size decreases [14]. Instrumentation 2θ value ranging from 10° to 80° and at a scanning rate

of $1^{\circ} \text{ min}^{-1}$ shown in **Figure 2.3** (Rigaku Smart Lab X-Ray Diffractometer) using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation source ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) at an operating voltage of 40 kV and current of 25 mA. The mean crystallite sizes of synthesised nanomaterials were calculated using Debye-Scherrer formula.

$$D = \frac{k\lambda}{\delta \cos\theta} \quad (2.2)$$

Where D is the crystallite size, k is Scherer's constant i.e., 0.94 for spherical particles, λ is the X-ray wavelength, β is the full peak width at half maximum intensity and θ is peak position.

Figure 2.3 Rigaku Smart Lab X-ray diffractometer

2.3.2 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

FTIR deals with the absorption of electromagnetic spectrum in the infrared region ($400\text{-}4000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Infrared radiation brings about changes in molecular vibrations within molecules so also termed as vibrational spectroscopy. Depending on atom size, bond length and strength, differs the frequency at which a specific bond absorbs infrared radiation. It undergoes permanent change in dipole when the infrared absorption takes place by the interaction of IR with the molecules. If the incoming infrared photons have enough required

energy for the upcoming allowed vibration energy state, then infrared absorption occurs. There are two types of vibrational modes. Vibrations undergo change in bond length named as stretching vibration and change in bond angle named as bending vibrations. Stretching vibrations occur along the line of the bond and bending vibrations do not occur along the line of the bond. A Bruker Alpha-P spectrometer has been used to obtain the FT-IR spectra shown in **Figure 2.4**. The analysis of samples was made using the KBr to make pellet. Then combined 2 mg of the prepared sample with 200 mg of KBr in an agate mortar. Used hydraulic pellet maker machine to obtain a translucent pellet.

Figure 2.4 Bruker alpha-FTIR spectrometer

2.3.3 Raman spectroscopy

Raman spectroscopy is a molecular spectroscopy that uses the interaction of light to reveal information about a material's composition or properties through light scattering process. It provides the intra- and inter molecular vibrations details of lower frequency. Rayleigh or elastic scattering takes place when the similar energy meets up in the dispersed photons of the material and incident. Energy within the molecule is remain unchanged and scattered photon wavelength equal to the incident photons ($\lambda_{\text{scatter}} = \lambda_{\text{laser}}$). Inelastic scattering or Raman effect occurs when the higher energy photons induce the polarization in the molecule, which in turn leaves the molecule at a higher energy state also termed as stokes Raman scattering ($\lambda_{\text{scatter}} > \lambda_{\text{laser}}$). Anti-stokes Raman scattering possible when the scattered radiation provides lower energy compared to incident laser light ($\lambda_{\text{scatter}} < \lambda_{\text{laser}}$). Raman analysis uses the laser of near UV or near IR or visible wavelengths. Either rotation or

vibrations results due to change in molecular polarizability. Instruments such as notch filters and adjustable filters are employed to increase the Raman signal because all incident photons undergo Rayleigh scattering and only about 0.001 % of photons induce inelastic scattering [15].

2.3.4 Diffuse reflectance UV-Visible spectroscopy (UV-DRS)

In order to obtain the reflectance of the solid samples UV-DRS has been taking into consideration by Perkin Elmer Lambda-35 Spectrophotometer (**Figure 2.5**). When the incident light is scattered at different angles on the surface of the material undergoes reflection. Kubelka-Munk (K-M) theory is used to obtain the typical absorption spectrum from the material. As per the absorption inflection point in the reflectance analysis considered as absorption host lattice in order to obtain the bandgap. The intercept of the tangents of photon energy versus $[F(R_\infty) h\nu]^{1/2}$ has been plotted. The K-M function $F(R_\infty)$ and photon energy ($h\nu$) are calculated by following equations.

$$F(R_\infty) = \frac{(1 - R_\infty)^2}{2R_\infty} \quad (2.3)$$

$$h\nu = \frac{1240}{\lambda} \quad (2.4)$$

Where R_∞ is reflection coefficient of the material, λ is the absorption wavelength. The optical band gap (E_g) has been calculated by

$$(F(R) h\nu)^n = A (h\nu - E_g) \quad (2.5)$$

Where A is constant, $h\nu$ is photon energy, as per the direct allowed transitions ($n=2$) and indirect allowed transitions ($n=1/2$).

Figure 2.5 Perkin Elmer Lamda-35 Spectrophotometer

2.3.5 UV-visible absorbance spectrophotometer

The difference in the energy levels of the molecules and electronic configuration provides the information of absorption wavelength. It is possible to define spectra in the ultraviolet and visible regions of radiation with absorption in the 200-800 nm range, a predictable UV-visible spectrophotometer. The wavelength is depending on the amount of energy absorbed by maximum absorption is UV-visible spectrophotometer. The absorption spectrum often supports qualitative identification. UV-vis absorption spectrum of NPs and the absorption of the dye solution were recorded with the Agilent Cary-60 technology (**Figure 2.6**).

Figure 2.6 Cary 60 UV-Vis Spectrophotometer

2.3.6 Thermo gravimetric and differential thermal analysis (TG-DTA)

The TG-DTA analysis was used to determine the thermal characteristics of the nanomaterials and helpful to observe the materials weight changes upon varying the temperature [39]. Sample characteristics including polymer degradation, material content, absorbed moisture temperatures, the quantity of organic and inorganic components also being analysed. TG-DTA technique analysed by Seiko Instruments Inc. EXSTAR6000 TG-DTA Thermogravimetric-Differential thermal analyser. Weight of the sample is being continuously recorded with the variation of temperature from 25 to 1000 °C at a heating rate of 2 °C min⁻¹ under O₂ atmosphere. DTA provides the difference in temperature between the sample and a thermally inert reference material. It measures as the samples temperature, during the transition period and the sample usually experiences energy liberation or absorption, which results in a temperature variation from the reference temperature [16].

2.3.7 Scanning electron microscope (SEM) with energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDAX)

Nano/microstructures size and morphology of the prepared NPs are obtained by SEM. SEM uses electrons rather than light to provide better images. It provides important 3-D images at a higher magnification than an optical magnifying device. SEM composed of electron gun, condenser lens, apertures, scan coils, objective lens, sample holder and detectors, VEGA 3 TESCAN SEM instrument and cross-sectional view of sample holder is shown in **Figure 2.7 (a and b)** [17]. Instrument works at 5-15 kV voltages and samples were gold covered for 2 min.

Figure 2.7 (a) Vega 3 Tescan SEM **(b)** Cross-sectional view of sample holder

EDAX tactic is incredibly innovative, particularly when it comes to the analysis of adulteration and contemporary scientific tests. It has a propensity to be arbitrary, semi-

quantitative and provides 3-D component conveyance through mapping in addition. It depends on how a sample and X-ray excitation interact. This characterization's essential tenet is that every element has a distinct atomic structure that allows for a distinct collection of peaks in its electromagnetic spectrum. This spectrum has been used in the most recent study to determine the elemental compositions of synthesized materials [18].

2.3.8 Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

To obtain the in-depth topographical images, the electrons are travel through the analysing samples in order to collect data. During the TEM examination, the entire area of the sample will undergo simultaneous electron irradiation. it is necessary to have an electron source that can generate more current. In most cases, the transmitted electrons are employed to create a diffraction pattern or obtain a material image. In a TEM, images of experiments could be captured using either regular imaging or high-goals imaging in turn it is termed as high-resolution transmission electron microscope (HR-TEM). In this study, a JEOL 3010 with acceleration voltage of 300 kV was employed. The instrument operates at a vacuum level of 10^{-6} Pa. High resolution of 0.14 nm and 0.12 nm point-to-point resolution can be achieved. To investigate the idea of the imperfection structure and the interplanar separation through SAED patterns operated between 20 to 200 kV voltage range [19].

2.3.9 Surface area analysis

Brunner- Emmett- Teller (BET) and Barret Joyner Halenda (BJH) methods (Nova Station 0) were used to study the surface area and pore diameter. The physisorbed moisture was removed on the prepared samples under vacuum at 363 K for 3 h and the physisorption study was performed using N₂ adsorption–desorption measurements at liquid N₂ temperature. The surface area, pore parameters and mean pore-size distributions of the prepared samples were computed.

2.3.10 Electrochemical cell

2.3.10.1 Preparation of electrodes

Prepared active materials, carbon black and polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) were pre-weighed according to 80:15:5 ratio respectively. A ceramic mortar-pestle was used to grind the aforementioned ingredients. To make a thin layer of slurry, a few drops of N-methyl pyrrolidinone (NMP) solvent were added. Along the way, the 16 mm diametric Cu (for anode)/Al (for cathode) was treated with 1 N HNO₃, acetone and distilled water for the deep

cleansing purpose. The resulting slurry was coated evenly on a dry Cu grid to preserve the ideal weight (2-4 mg/cm²). Finally, the crack-free uniform coating was achieved once after the vacuum drying at 100 °C.

2.3.10.2 Cell assembly

The assembly of the coin cells (CR2032) was carried out in an argon-filled glove box (MBraun Model Unilab). Vacuum dried electrodes were weighed to measure the actual weight of the active materials on the substrates. On a press machine, the weighed electrodes were pressed in between the two dies at a pressure of around 200 kg cm⁻². Inside the glove box, moisture and oxygen levels were always controlled within 0.5 ppm in an argon atmosphere to avoid oxidation. The metal lithium was used as a reference electrode, to avoid electrical contact between the electrodes, a separator (Celgard porous polypropylene membrane - 2400) was utilised. The electrolyte (1 M LiPF₆) was dissolved in 2: 2: 1 ratio of ethylene carbonate, dimethyl carbonate and diethyl carbonate.

2.3.10.3 Electrochemical techniques

The fabricated testing cells were electrochemically examined through systematic analysis of the active materials. The electrochemical studies generally include several techniques, including cyclic voltammetry, galvanostatic charge-discharge and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, all of which are discussed in detail below and the overall electrochemical performances were evaluated based on the obtained results.

A set of typical battery tests were carried out using eight channelled Biologic potentiostat/galvanostat (BCS 805), (**Figure 2.8**) the battery test unit. Cyclic voltammogram (CV) is a sort of potentiodynamic electrochemical measurement, that records a current-voltage relationship when the potential at the working electrode is raised linearly versus time (at a set scan rate). At the same sweep rate, reversed back to the original potential. A single or a few scans will take-up to analyse the electrochemical properties. In the particular voltage range, analyte may oxidized/reduced, polarity showed by sign with a sweep rate (0.1 mV/s) and discharge potential (0.01-3 V) vs lithium insertion and exertion, CV was carried out for the assembled cells. Galvanostatic discharge-charge study was examined by applying constant current to test the cell and analysed the columbic efficiency and long-term cycling properties.

Figure 2.8 Battery testing unit

2.3.11 Experimental set-up and procedure of photocatalytic dye degradation

The degradation of various cationic and anionic dyes in aqueous medium under 250 W UV light irradiation was used to examine the photocatalytic study of prepared nanomaterials. **Figure 2.9** explains the (a) experimental setup for the photocatalytic dye degradation (b) top view of the photocatalytic dye degradation chamber for photocatalytic investigations, a visible annular photoreactor was used (HEBER scientific in Chennai, India). The photocatalytic reactor composed of light source in the middle and it is surrounded by eight 100 mL quartz reactor tubes with the cooling fans.

Figure 2.9 (a) Experimental setup for the photocatalytic dye degradation (b) Top view the photocatalytic dye degradation chamber

Photocatalytic dye degradation study has been carried out with 50 mg of the prepared photocatalyst in 5 ppm dye. The experiment begins in the dark for 30 min without switch on the source for the aeration irradiation. Reaction solution was collected for every 30 min.

Collected sample was centrifuged to measure the absorbance in a UV-Vis absorption spectrophotometer. The percentage of degradation was calculated using the equation below.

$$\% \text{ of degradation} = [(C_0 - C_t) / C_0] \times 100 \quad (2.6)$$

Initial and final concentrations are noted as C_0 and C_t

2.3.12 Experimental set-up and procedure of electrochemical nitrite sensing

Electrochemical nitrite sensing uses the glassy carbon electrode (GCE) for the modification with the prepared catalyst. Therefore, GCE has been polished with the alumina suspension, then washed with the distilled water followed by ethanol. For the modification, ultrasonicated the 10 mg of the prepared material in 2 mL distilled water for 30 min. Drip coated the ultrasonicated sample on to the GCE. The electro-catalytic analysis of the prepared sample was carried out in CH instrument containing three electrode system of reference electrode (Ag/AgCl), working electrode (Prepared material) and counter electrode (platinum disc). **Figure 2.10** (a and b) shows the experimental set up and electrochemical workstation (CHI 660D Austin USA).

Figure 2.10 (a) Experimental set up (b) Electrochemical workstation (CHI 660D Austin USA) of nitrite sensing

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CHAPTER - III

Energy storage, Photocatalytic
and Electrochemical nitrite
sensing of ultrasound-assisted
Stable Ta₂O₅ Nanoparticles

3.1 Introduction

Due to the high extrinsic pseudocapacitance, Ta₂O₅ electrode material has been considered as advanced anode for energy storage application. Ta₂O₅ is safe electrode material and environmentally benign with a theoretical discharge capacity of 482 mA h g⁻¹ for Li⁺ storage. Some downsides of the Ta₂O₅ anode include a poorer conductivity and a fluctuating plateau during intercalation-deintercalation process [1]. The term "bandgap" refers to the anodically created Ta₂O₅ is 4 eV optical energy [2]. Due to its strong chemical stability for the elimination of dye impurities and capability to increase solar absorption property made by Ta₂O₅, become very promising photocatalyst as well [3]. The inadequate selectivity of the bare electrode can be enhanced by modifying with the GCE to get the appropriate sensitivity and selectivity. In most cases, the intermediate nitrite molecules never enter GCE. Tryptophan, ascorbic acid, uric acid and oxytetracycline have all been diligently detected using Ta₂O₅ NPs with a variety of dopants and with carbon derivatives [4-6]. Unique ultrasonication technique has been adopted with the aprotic solvent DMSO (dimethyl sulfoxide) to synthesise Ta₂O₅ nanoparticles (NPs) of porous structure along with the features signifying the biocompatibility, biodegradability, and non-toxicity [7]. For the purpose of developing high-capacity anode, photocatalytic material and for nitrite sensing electrocatalyst, particles are tailored by optimising the experimental conditions. Uniform particles dispersion and subsequent nucleation are implied to the ultrasonication process, which is based on the chemical reactions of the solution.

3.2 Experimental

3.2.1 Ta₂O₅ nanoparticles (NPs)

Absolute ethanol (20 mL) solution was evenly mixed with 0.5 g of TaCl₅ precursor for the complete dissolution. After the even dispersion, added 1 mL of distilled water and 5 mL of the DMSO solvent. The resulting solution was kept in a sonicator for the thermal agitation, with the 20 KHz higher frequency and 70 W power for 60 min. To remove the contaminants, the resulting precipitate was allowed to go through centrifugation using distilled water and then ethanol. The leftover sediment was vacuum-dried at 70 °C for 6 h. The Ta₂O₅ NPs were produced by calcining the obtained powder sample at 800 °C for 2 h in the air.

3.3 Results and discussion

Figure 3.1 XRD pattern of ultrasonic-assisted Ta_2O_5 of (a) standard (b) as synthesized (c) commercial (d) calcined NPs

Figure 3.1 shows the comparison of calcined, commercial, as-synthesised Ta_2O_5 NPs XRD patterns with the standard JCPDS card no. 5-258 [8]. The orthorhombic phase is indicated by the XRD pattern of Ta_2O_5 NPs and an average crystallite size of 13 nm is determined.

Figure 3.2 FTIR spectra of ultrasonic-assisted Ta_2O_5 for as-prepared, commercial and calcined

The FTIR spectra of calcined, commercial and as-prepared Ta₂O₅ NPs is displayed in **Figure 3.2**. Calcined and commercial particles exhibited the Ta-O and Ta-O-Ta stretching vibration modes at below 1000 cm⁻¹. Stretching and bending hydroxyl vibrations are shown by sharp bands at 3443 cm⁻¹ and 1631 cm⁻¹ respectively [9].

Figure 3.3 (a) Diffuse reflectance (b) Band gap energy plots of calcined Ta₂O₅ NPs

The DRS graph of Ta₂O₅ NPs produced at RT is shown in **Figure 3.3 (a)**. Using the Kubelka-Munk (K-M) hypothesis, the absorption inflection point occurred around 300 nm [10]. The photon energy's intercept of the tangents vs. $[F(R) hv]^{1/2}$ was displayed in the **Figure 3.3 (b)**. 4.07 eV is the obtained E_g value the Ta₂O₅ NPs.

Figure 3.4 (a) N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherm of BET (b) BJH pore size distribution of calcined Ta₂O₅ NPs

Brunauer Emmett Teller (BET) surface area analysis and Barrett Joyner Halenda (BJH) pore size distribution graphs are used to analyze the prepared Ta₂O₅ NPs. The calcined

Ta₂O₅ NPs were found to have a specific BET surface area of 26.70 m²/g. The measured BJH pore diameter is 1.48 nm indicates the presence of micropores. This predicted outcome is consistent with type II hysteresis [11].

Figure 3.5 TGA-DTA curves of as-prepared Ta₂O₅ NPs

Figure 3.5 displayed the TGA-DTA curves of Ta₂O₅ NPs. Due to weight loss of 5 %, the sample began to deteriorate and the decomposition of organic components occurred between 200 and 650 °C. When Ta₂O₅ NPs underwent the required phase transitions in the mid regime of 650 and 750 °C, there was a 3 % weight loss. The temperature at which the phase shifts is explained by the DTA profile at 716 °C. High temperature calcination helpful for the removal of grain boundaries and to increase the crystallite size. High surface area and stability can be observed above the annealing temperature, which is 750 °C [12].

Figure 3.6 (a) SEM and (b) EDS of calcined Ta₂O₅ NPs

The SEM image (**Figure 3.6 (a)**) demonstrates the dense agglomeration of the particles and the presence of very small crystals that resemble a flakes, are in the micron range. EDS graph (**Figure 3.6 (b)**) confirmed the presence of all the elements.

Ta₂O₅ nanoparticles had an average particle size of 10 nm according to TEM images. The SAED pattern by TEM pictures (**Figure 3.7 (a and b)**) verified the interlayer spacing of 0.23 nm, demonstrating the increasing direction along (1 11 1) in HRTEM images **Figure 3.7 (c and d)**.

Figure 3.7 (a & b) TEM (c) HRTEM images and (d) SAED pattern of Ta₂O₅ NPs

The typical CV of Ta₂O₅ NPs at 0.1 mV s⁻¹ sweep rate in the potential range of 0.1 to 3.0 V vs. lithium-ion intercalation-deintercalation is shown in **Figure 3.8**. The cell displayed 3.1 V open circuit voltage. Lithium ions were intercalated into the Ta₂O₅ anode from 3.0 V to

0.1 V; the highest lithiation occurred between 1 V and 0.5 V. First lithiation cycle reduction potentials at 0.45, 1.2 and 1.5 V are apparent when the sweep starts at 3.0 V [1].

Figure 3.8 Cyclic voltammogram of Ta₂O₅ NPs

A large peak near 1 V during the reverse scan revealed the de-lithiation process. The fact that subsequent cycles proceeded in the same manner validated both the reversibility of lithiation and the de-lithiation process. Peaks vanished in the following cycles, explaining the formation of solid-electrolyte interface (SEI) as a result of the degradation of the electrolyte. Additionally, more electrolyte would be consumed due to the availability of more active sites [13]. It is evident that Ta₂O₅ NPs have attained reversibility as of the third cycle. The large peak at 1.2 V during a cathodic scan and 0.7 V during an anodic scan signifies the reversible response of the lithiation and de-lithiation process (**Eq. 3.1**).

Reversibility of the electrode has been confirmed by overlapping the current humps by the subsequent cycles.

The Ta₂O₅ electrode's galvanostatic charge-discharge profile at a C/10 rate of 0.1-3 V vs. Li/Li⁺ is shown in **Figure 3.10**. The initial irreversible discharge plateau indicated a capacity of 652 mA h g⁻¹. The obtained first charge and discharge capacity are 452 and of 446 mA h g⁻¹ respectively. The observed capacity loss may be attributed to the volume increase as

well as the growth of the Li_2O and SEI layers. After 50 cycles, the specific capacity has stabilized and there isn't any capacity loss notified. The Ta_2O_5 electrode has a specific discharge capacity of 192 mA h g^{-1} at the 200th cycle.

Figure 3.9 Galvanostatic charge-discharge profile of Ta_2O_5 NPs at C/10 current rate

Figure 3.10 Cycling performance and Coulombic efficiency of Ta_2O_5 NPs at C/10 rate

Figure 3.10 depicts the cycle life and coulombic efficiency. At a C/10 rate, the coulombic efficiency is closer to 100 % for up to 200 cycles. The initial lithiation capacity is 652 mA h g^{-1} and it decreased by 30 % for each subsequent cycle. After 50 rounds of the discharging-charging process, stability has been preserved. By the end of

200 cycles, 86 percent of the initial discharge capacity has been preserved. The rate capability of the **Figure 3.11** shows the Ta₂O₅ electrode at various current densities. At first, the discharge capacity degrades after 6 cycles of operation at C/10 current density, going from 340 to 280 mA h g⁻¹.

Figure 3.11 Rate capability of calcined Ta₂O₅ NPs at different current rates

Table 3.1 describes the comparison of electrochemical performance of prepared Ta₂O₅ with the available literature.

Table 3.1. Electrochemical performance of Ta ₂ O ₅ nanocomposite				
Material with structure	Method	Initial discharge capacity (mA h g⁻¹)	Capacity (mA h g⁻¹) /Cycles (times) @ current density mA g⁻¹	References
Mesoporous Ta ₂ O ₅ NPs	Hydrothermal	509	152/50, @ 0.1 C	[1]
Ta ₂ O ₅ film	Pulsed laser deposition	100	411/ 100 @ 20 μA/cm ²	[2]
Ta ₂ O ₅ aerogels	Sol-gel	990	63/2000 @ 5000	[3]
Ta ₂ O ₅ NPs	Hydrothermal	440	130/ 85 @ 0.1C	[4]
Ta ₂ O ₅ thin films	e-beam evaporation	170	260/100 @ 1C	[5]
Ta ₂ O ₅ NPs	Ultra-sonication	1365	252/100 @ 0.1 C	This work

The photocatalytic study of calcined, commercial and as-synthesized Ta₂O₅ NPs by the degradation of MB dye under visible light source is shown in **Figure 3.12**. Calcined Ta₂O₅ NPs have capable to degrade very high percentage (94 %) of MB dye compared to as-prepared and commercial Ta₂O₅ NPs.

Figure 3.12 Percentage degradation of Methylene blue dye for calcined, commercial and as-prepared Ta₂O₅ NPs

Figure 3.13 (a) explains the Cyclic Voltammetry (CV) graph comparing the Ta₂O₅-modified GCE with the unmodified GCE electrode. **Figure 3.13 (b)** the dependable Linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) with its calibration graph **(c)**. Ta₂O₅ modified GCE has been encountered to obtain both qualitative and quantitative data from nitrite species sampling by adjusting concentration with respect to current [14-16]. For the detection of 5 mM nitrite, CV and LSV have been used with $1.e^{-006}$ sensitivity and within the 10-100 mV/s range.

Figure 3.13 (a) Cyclic voltammogram (b) Linear sweep voltammogram (c) calibration plot of Ta_2O_5 NPs

3.4 Conclusion

Ta_2O_5 nanoparticles have been effectively produced by sonochemical method using DMSO as an aprotic solvent for applications in rechargeable batteries, photocatalysis and electrochemical nitrite detection. Delivered a discharge capacity of 192 mA h g^{-1} for 200 cyclic rotations at a C/10 rate. Ta_2O_5 NPs capable to degrade 94 % of methylene blue (MB) dye due to large surface area and a modest bandgap. Ta_2O_5 modified glassy carbon electrode (GCE) exhibited a detection limit of $2.369 \mu\text{M}$ towards 5 mM nitrite.

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CHAPTER - IV

High capacitive
h-MoO₃ hexagonal rods
and its applications
towards Lithium-ion
Battery and Nitrite sensing

4.1 Introduction

Molybdenum is the refractory transition metal, known for its extensive, exceptional industrial use because to its high melting point, high temperature, limited thermal expansion, and low vapour pressure. It also has a high electrical and thermal conductivity. For its use in electrochemical storage devices, sensors, catalysts, lubricants and smart windows, molybdenum trioxide is particularly intriguing. Metastable h-MoO₃ is one of the MoO₃ polymorphs now in existence, is made up of an anisotropic zigzag pattern in which MoO₆ octahedrons share corner edges and are joined by cis-positions. However, h-MoO₃ has a theoretical capacity of 1117 mA h g⁻¹ and exhibits remarkable phase stability when compared to orthorhombic and monoclinic-MoO₃ [1, 2]. The rate capability of h-MoO₃ electrode materials is hampered by poor kinetics caused by Li⁺ diffusion. Tuning the MoO₃ morphology to obtain the various structures of nanowires, porous films and nanoflowers will help to overcome from the drawbacks [3-5]. In this instance, we have opted for the straightforward reflux approach to produce self-assembled, hexagonal micro rods shaped h-MoO₃ nanomaterial. The reflux method offers various benefits over other solution phase techniques, including safety, simplicity of procedure and high yield (95 %).

4.2 Experimental

4.2.1 Preparation of h-MoO₃ hexagonal rods

A 50 mL of DD (double distilled) water was used to dissolve the ammonium heptamolybdate (1.029 gm) precursor. Then, urea (0.0634 gm) was gradually added under continuous stirring for about 30 min to produce a clear solution. Again, stirred for the next 30 min while adding 2 mL of HCl. Additionally, the mixture was refluxed on the magnetic hotplate for a day at 40 °C (without stirring). An airtight container was used to hold the acquired dark blue powder.

4.3 Results and discussion

Figure 4.1 displays the XRD pattern of the hexagonal rod shaped called h-MoO₃ nanomaterial. These planes match the hexagonal crystal structure with the JCPDS card number (21-569) and by the Debye-Scherrer formula, obtained a crystallite size value of 52 nm.

Figure 4.1 XRD pattern of h-MoO₃ hexagonal rods

The hexagonal rod-shaped h-MoO₃ nanomaterial's FTIR spectrum is shown in **Figure 4.2**. The recognizable peaks at 510, 860 and 981 cm⁻¹ can be noticed in the graph. The bending modes of Mo-O-Mo are responsible for the absorption peak at 981 cm⁻¹. The terminal bonds of Mo=O are thought to be responsible for the vibrational peak at 510 cm⁻¹. The Mo-O vibrations are responsible for the peak at 860 cm⁻¹. The stretching and bending vibrations of the -OH bond is responsible for the peaks at 3435 cm⁻¹ and 1637 cm⁻¹, respectively [6].

Figure 4.2 FTIR patterns of h-MoO₃ hexagonal rods

Figure 4.3 shows the prepared hexagonal rod-shaped h-MoO₃ nanomaterial's UV-Vis DRS spectra. The host lattice absorption peak is thought to be responsible for the maximum, highly intense band at 340 nm [7]. 3.48 eV is the E_g value that was determined using the plot using Kubelka-Munk equation.

Figure 4.3 DRS patterns of h-MoO₃ hexagonal rods

Figure 4.4 displays SEM images of hexagonal rod-shaped h-MoO₃ nanomaterial at progressively higher magnifications. All the h-MoO₃ particles took the shape of hexagonal rods. A collection of hexagonal rods in varying sizes are joined to form bunches. These delicate structures, which are projected a few long rods measuring between 5 and 7.5 micrometres, are in the micro range. Numerous short (2.5 μ m) rods are self-organized into flower-like clusters.

Figure 4.4 SEM images of h-MoO₃ hexagonal rods

The Li⁺ intercalation into crystalline h-MoO₃ resulting in the creation of Li_xMoO₃ compound and solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) layer, respectively, is shown in the **Figure 4.5**. Two irreversible cathodic, reduction peaks formed at 1.78 and 0.09 V. Due to the creation of the SEI layer and Li₂O, the capacity begins to degrade. For practical purpose, pre-lithiation of the electrode can reduce the decomposition. The most active peak is the redox couple peak located at 1.78 V. Li₂O and metallic Mo are produced as a result of the reaction between Li_xMoO₃ and Li⁺ ion, represents as strong cathodic peak at 0.09 V. The crystal structure did not fully recover following the initial discharge. Hence, cathodic peaks at 1.24 and 0.42 V in the subsequent cycles suggest the lithiation of the h-MoO₃ anode. Around 1.78 V, there is one more peak that is attributed to the oxidation of lithium ions. Peaks in the 10th cycle are almost diminished because of the crystal structural change [8].

Figure 4.5 Cyclic voltammogram of h-MoO₃ hexagonal rods

Figure 4.6 illustrates the charge-discharge performance of the h-MoO₃ anode, explaining the initial, first, 25th, 50th and 100th cycles with a C/15 rate between the voltage window of 0.01-3.0 V vs. Li/Li⁺. Hexagonal rod-shaped h-MoO₃ exhibited an initial discharge capacity of 1869 mA h g⁻¹. The insertion of the Li⁺ ion into the h-MoO₃ crystal lattice is represented by the first discharge peak at 2.0 V and the redox reaction occurs at 1.5 V. In the subsequent 6 cycles, the structure of the active material is totally changed into an amorphous state, producing smooth curves. The following discharge capacity curves are shown at 1376, 818, 730 and 619 mA h g⁻¹ respectively, for the first, twenty-fifth, fifty-first and one hundredth cycles. The lithiation process is thought to be responsible for the plateaus at 0.93, 0.47 and 0.18 V.

Figure 4.6 Galvanostatic Discharge-charge profile of h-MoO₃ hexagonal rods

In the **Figure 4.7**, the data indicated that the initially reversible capacity has decreased for few cycles before stabilising at 750 mA h g⁻¹. Even after 100 cycles, roughly 48 % of the specific capacity remained. Coulombic efficiency of the anode varied about 1-2 percent somewhere in the range of cycling before stabilising at 100 percent efficiency.

Figure 4.7 Cyclic performance and Coulombic efficiency profile of h-MoO₃ hexagonal rods

Figure 4.8 illustrates different C-rates for each 5 cycles to determine the rate capability. For the C-rates of C/15, C/10, C/5, 1C, C/5, C/10 and C/15 obtained discharge capacities are 1162.34, 988.12, 466.61, 697.60, 759.47 and 782.73 mA h g⁻¹ respectively.

Figure 4.8 Rate capability of h-MoO₃ hexagonal rods

Table 4.1 explains the comparative study of h-MoO₃ nanomaterials. Prepared h-MoO₃ hexagonal rod-shaped material shows highest initial discharge capacity and maintained stable capacity even after 100 cycles at C/15 compared to other materials.

Table 4.1. Electrochemical performance of h-MoO ₃ hexagonal rods			
Nanostructure	Initial discharge capacity (mA h g ⁻¹)	Capacity (mAhg ⁻¹) / Cycles (times) @ current density mA g ⁻¹	References
h-MoO ₃ nanorods	1418.3	780/150 @ 150	[9]
MoO _{3-x} nanowire array	770	590/20 @ 100	[3]
MoO ₃ porous film	800	450/50 @ 1C	[4]
α-MoO ₃ nanoflowers	1432.5	810.7/100 @ 550	[5]
α-MoO ₃ nanorods	1461.3	169/100 @ 550	
h-MoO ₃ hexagonal rods	1869	619 / 100 @ C/15	This work

The h-MoO₃ electrocatalyst's sensing application is examined using electrochemical techniques including CV and LSV. From the CV in **Figure 4.9 (a)**, we can see that the h-MoO₃ modified GCE has a higher current (0.19 to 0.22 mA) than the un-modified electrode. The current at oxidation potential has linearly increased as the scan rate has increased. By

having a regression coefficient for the oxidation of 0.99, the diffusion-controlled process has been accomplished. The Linear sweep voltammogram (LSV) **Figure 4.9 (b)** was created by changing the nitrite ion concentration (from 100 to 1200 M) while using a modified GCE with h-MoO₃ in phosphate buffer at pH 7.

Figure 4.9 (a) Cyclic voltammograms bare and h-MoO₃ modified GCE **(b)** Linear sweep voltammograms of h-MoO₃ modified GCE at different concentrations of phosphate buffer (pH=7)

4.4 Conclusion

Hexagonal rods shaped h-MoO₃ nanomaterial has been made using a simple, low temperature reflux technique. The performance of the h-MoO₃ nanomaterial has been investigated through structural, morphological and electrochemical applications. The h-MoO₃ electrode has outstanding stability at a current rate of C/15 over 100 cycles as well as a high discharge capacity of 619 mA h g⁻¹. Modified glassy carbon electrode containing h-MoO₃ have demonstrated the detection limit of 0.196 μM for 1 mM nitrite.

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CHAPTER - V

Sonochemical synthesis
of $\text{SnO}_2\text{-CuO}$
Nanocomposite:
diverse applications on
Li-ion battery,
Electrochemical sensing
and Photocatalytic activity

5.1 Introduction

According to the literature, Tin oxide (SnO_2) is a benefic anode battery material due to its massive theoretical capacity of 790 mA h g^{-1} , stability and safety. The alloying/ de-alloying process of SnO_2 results in pulverization, additional lithium utilization and irreversible capacity, whereas SnO_2 failed to demonstrate the structural integrity, rate capability and intrinsic conductivity [1, 2]. In comparison to single metal oxides, SnO_2 integrated metal oxide composites result a larger surface area and faster pathways to LIBs topotactical activity. The stability and life span can be increased by managing the volume expansion. Copper oxide (CuO) is a very fascinating current collector and has a high theoretical capacity of 674 mA h g^{-1} . It will enable the more effective conversion reaction from CuO to Cu at the nanoscale. CuO also undergoes volume changing during the discharge-charge process, which reduces cycle performance. Zero-dimensional SnO_2 NPs and CuO NPs composites play a significant role in resolving the pulverisation problem and the SnO_2 - CuO nanocomposite demonstrates a capacity twice as high as the specific capacity of graphite [3]. SnO_2 exhibits the high photosensitivity, non-toxicity and wide bandgap (3.7 eV, n-type) and CuO exhibits narrow bandgap (p type, 1.5 eV). These semiconducting materials can be coupled to produce good catalytic activity by increasing the charge carrier separation in the photo responding region [4]. The effectiveness of carrier separation can be increased because CuO serves as a sink for electrons, while photogenerated holes flow in the opposite direction to collect in the valence band of SnO_2 .

5.2 Experimental

5.2.1 SnO_2 - CuO nanocomposite synthesis

The ultrasonication approach was used to form the binary compound SnO_2 - CuO . Equal proportions (0.5 M) of tin chloride ($\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and copper nitrate ($\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were liquify in distilled water. To each solution, added 1 M NaOH dropwise. For the complete particle's agitation, two solutions were sonicated for 30 min, then combined and sonicated for 1 h. To remove NaCl peaks, the precipitate was centrifuged with ethanol and distilled water. Dried the settled sample at 80°C . The final product was obtained after the calcination at 500°C for 2 h.

5.3. Results and Discussion

Figure 5.1 depicts the SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite's XRD pattern. SnO₂ represents the tetragonal phase as per JCPDS No: 1-657 and CuO NPs signifies the monoclinic phase according to JCPDS No: 1-1117. The crystalline nature of the SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite is confirmed by sharp peaks. According to the Debye-Sherrer formula, the obtained mean crystalline sizes for the SnO₂ and CuO phases are 10 and 16 nm respectively.

Figure 5.1 XRD pattern of SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite

The FTIR spectrum of the SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite is shown in **Figure 5.2**. The IR active modes are located at 530 cm⁻¹ signifies the Sn-O-Sn and Sn-O vibrations and the peak centred at 603 cm⁻¹ ascribed the presence of CuO. H-O-H and O-H stretching modes represented by 3408 and 1623 cm⁻¹ peaks [5, 6].

Figure 5.2 FTIR plot of SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite

Further Raman spectroscopy has confirmed the existence of SnO₂ and CuO bands (Figure 5.3). The SnO₂, SnO₂ (E_g), SnO₂ (A_{1g}), and SnO₂ (B_{2g}) Raman vibration modes centered at 160, 479, 609 and 758 cm⁻¹ respectively. The bands located at 635 and 290 cm⁻¹ corresponds to CuO (B_g) and CuO (A_g) vibrations [7].

Figure 5.3 Raman spectrum of SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite

The N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherm is explained in Figure 5.4 and the BJH in the inset plot. The Type II isotherm is indicated by a long adsorption deviation. The calculated surface area and mean pore diameter are 23.29 m²/g and 6.31 nm respectively. The mesoporous nature of the produced particles is shown by the pore diameter.

Figure 5.4 N₂ adsorption and desorption isotherm (BET) and corresponding pore size distribution BJH (inset) plots of SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite

The UV-DRS graph of the SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite is given in **Figure 5.5 (a)**. At 300 nm, there was an absorption inflection point that may be attributed to host lattice absorption. The Kubelka-Munk (K-M) hypothesis is used to estimate the bandgap (E_g). The intercept of the tangents of photon energy versus $[F(R)]^2$ is shown in the plot of **Figure 5.5 (b)**. The obtained E_g value is 5.2 eV for the SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite.

Figure 5.5 (a) Diffuse reflectance **(b)** Band gap energy plots of SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite

SEM images are used to study the topographical images of the SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite. SEM images of the SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite are shown in **Figure 5.6**. Particles aggregations are visible and micron sized crystals are spread over the agglomerated groupings.

Figure 5.6 (a and b) SEM images of SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite

The EDS plot shown in **Figure 5.7** confirmed that the Sn, Cu and O elements are present.

Figure 5.7 EDS spectrum and elemental composition (inset) of SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite

Figure 5.8 (a and b) displays TEM images of SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite. Particles that are spherical and clearly scattered within 11–15 nm range. The HR-TEM images (**Figure 5.8 (c and d)**) explain SAED pattern validates the crystallinity and the phases that correspond to it are labelled.

Figure 5.8 (a, b) TEM images (c) d-spacing (d) SAED pattern of SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite

The cyclic voltammogram (CV) curves of a SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite for ten cycles, performed at a potential window of 0 to 3 V versus lithiation-delithiation process, are shown in **Figure 5.9**. Multistep electrochemical processes took place; the reduction reaction is represented by cathodic peaks centered at 1.56 and 0.77 V corresponds to the conversion reaction between CuO and SnO₂, while the oxidation reaction is represented by anodic peaks centred at 0.49, 1.3 and 2.44 V corresponds to alloying reactions. The corresponding cycles follow the three plateau regions. No significant differences are discernible, which is attributable to the preservation of structural stability. Compositing can be used to explain the short cycle life of anode material. The lithiation and de-lithiation processes of topotactic conversion reactions have effectively taken place for the intended reversibility. The matching reduction and oxidation peaks are followed by each of the ten cycles.

Figure 5.9 Cyclic voltammogram of SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite

Figure 5.10 shows the charge-discharge profile of the SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite for the initial, first, second, tenth, twenty-fifth, fifty-fifth and hundredth cycles at C/10 rate between the voltage range of 0 and 3 V vs Li/Li⁺. Initial discharge capacity of 1365 mA h g⁻¹ exhibited by SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite. Due to the creation of the interfacial solid electrolyte interface, the discharge capacity drastically decreased till 50 cycles and retained 252 mA h g⁻¹ discharged capacity at 100th cycle.

Figure 5.10 Galvanostatic discharge-charge cycles of SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite

The SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite's cyclic discharge-charge stability and Coulombic efficiency for 100 cycles at C/10 rate is shown in **Figure 5.11**. This has retained 20 % capacity at the 100th cycle. Throughout the 100 cycles, the Coulombic efficiency stabilised around 99 percent.

Figure 5.11 Cyclic performance and Coulombic efficiency of SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite

The rate capacity of the SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite is shown in **Figure 5.12** at C/15, C/10, C/5, 1C and 2C for each five cycles and lastly C/5 for 50 cycles. The stability has achieved with the variation in rate capability. At a rate of C/15, C/10, C/5, 1C and 2C, respectively, the SnO₂-CuO anode displays reversible capacities of 300, 240, 180, 130 and 90 mA h g⁻¹.

Figure 5.12 Rate capability of SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite

After a continuous 100 charge-discharge cycles, the SnO₂-CuO anode has been examined for the stability by the XRD plot shown in **Figure 5.13**. As per the JCPDS No # 31-761, 36-1074, 2 θ values at 21.25 and 39.77 ° assigned to Li₂SnO₃, LiCuO respectively and Li metal peak at 36.25 °. As per the JCPDS No # 18-753 the peak centered at 23.35 ° confirmed the LiSn. According to the JCPDS No # 12-254, confirmed the formation of Li₂O peak occurred at 33.91 °.

Figure 5.13 XRD pattern of electrode after 100 charge-discharge cycles of SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite

Table 5.1 explains the comparison of electrochemical performances of SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite developed by different methods.

Table 5.1 Electrochemical performance of SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite

Material with structure	Method	Initial discharge capacity (mA h g ⁻¹)	Capacity (mA h g ⁻¹) / Cycles (times) @ current density mA g ⁻¹	References
SnO ₂ -CuO (5:1) Nanotubes	Electrospinning	917	592.3/120, 500	[8]
CuO/SnO ₂	Thermal annealing on Cu foils	1645	718/ 200, 500	[9]
SnO ₂ -CuO/graphite	Hydrothermal	2480	584/30 @ 0.1 C	[10]
SnO ₂ -CuO nanocomposite	Co-precipitation	1500	752/60, 0.1C	[11]
SnO ₂ -CuO-graphite, Nanosheets	Bead milling	1172.8	561.2/ 150, 0.1C	[12]
SnO ₂ -CuO, nanoparticles	Ultra-sonication	1365	252/100, 0.1 C	This work

Using cyclic voltammetry (CV) and linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) approaches, the electrochemical behaviour of a SnO₂-CuO GCE is examined in the range of 10-100 mV/s with 1.e⁻⁰⁰⁶ sensitivity for nitrite oxidation. The cyclic voltammogram of the SnO₂-CuO-modified electrode for the electro-oxidation of 1 mM nitrite is shown in **Figure 5.14 (a)**. An oxidation peak current response at 50 μ A was seen in the bare GCE. With the rise in peak current of 75 μ A shown in **Figure 5.14 (b)**. The SnO₂-CuO-modified GCE have significantly higher current density than the un-modified GCE. The increased electrocatalytic activity is attributed to the availability of additional active sites with high surface area. Sensing of nitrite in the concentration range of 100-1500 M in KCl buffer of pH 7 at the scan rate of 50 mV/s using an electrode modified with SnO₂-CuO. The oxidation peak current rises linearly with the rise in nitrite content, as can be seen by carefully observing LSV curves. The anodic peak current vs nitrite concentration calibration plot was created using a detection limit of 0.825 μ M. The GCE modified SnO₂-CuO has showed an improvement in electrocatalytic activity for the detection of nitrite.

Figure 5.14 (a) Cyclic voltammograms (b) Linear sweep voltammograms and (c) calibration plot of bare and SnO₂-CuO modified glassy carbon electrode at different concentrations of phosphate buffer (pH=7)

It has been examined how well the SnO₂-CuO photocatalyst degrades the dyes of methyl orange (MO) and methylene blue (MB) when exposed to UV light. When the light interaction commences, the actual mechanism begins. If the incident energy is greater than the threshold bandgap, the photon energy will be absorbed by the SnO₂-CuO semiconductor (5.2 eV). The three main elements that will contribute to enhancing the photocatalytic action are particle size, bandgap and surface area. According to **Figure 5.15 (a)**, the degradation of the MB dye in the presence of the photocatalyst has caused a gradual decrease in the absorption peak at 662 nm. In the presence of SnO₂-CuO nanophotocatalyst under UV light exposure, the efficiency of cationic (MB) and anionic (MO) dye degradation has achieved 86 and 47 % respectively (**Figure 5.15 (b)**).

Figure 5. 15 (a) UV absorbance spectra of MB dye **(b)** Percentage degradation of Methylene blue and Methylene orange dye for SnO₂-CuO photocatalyst

5.4 Conclusion

By summarising this chapter, Applications of SnO₂-CuO binary nanocomposite include photocatalytic dye degradation, electrochemical nitrite detection and lithium-ion batteries prepared through the ultrasonication process. XRD, FTIR, Raman spectroscopy and EDS are used to confirm the presence of SnO₂ and CuO compounds. The evidence for the occurrence of a stable irreversible reaction is found in the cyclic voltammogram. It has a high initial discharge capacity of 1365 mA h g⁻¹ and the corresponding first, second, tenth, twenty-fifth, fifty-first and hundredth discharge-charge capacities are 854, 754, 695, 480, 322 and 252 mA h g⁻¹ respectively.

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CHAPTER - VI

Exploring the *Spondias mombin* (Hog plum) mediated
 ZnWO_4 - CuWO_4
Nanocomposite for
Photocatalysis and
Electrochemical nitrite sensing

6.1 Introduction

Tungstates are a type of visible light-responsive photocatalysts that can be used to degrade the organic dye contaminants of water. Single metal tungstate will undergo recombination of photo-induced electron-hole pairs, which will hinder the wide range of applications. Binary tungstates are considered due to the eco-friendliness and greater stability. They are being investigated for environmental cleaning and energy storage applications [1]. Binary heterojunctions enhanced the photocatalytic activity due to effective charge carriers' separation and increase the range of light absorption [2]. Transition metal tungstate's have significant stability in acid environments; therefore, have become the efficient photo degradation materials towards dye effluents [3]. Self-luminescent material of Zinc tungstate (ZnWO_4) acts as good photocatalyst. It has high refractive index, good electrochemical properties and non-toxic. Hence, nowadays widely used in applications such as photocatalysis, heterogenous catalysis, radiation detector etc., due to its wide band gap energy of 3.9 eV [4]. ZnWO_4 has a $d^{10}s^2-d^0$ electron configuration, due to its restricted spectrum scope, inefficient hole-electron separation and often shows poor activity in compared to other metal tungstates [5]. Unique physical and chemical characteristics made tungstates to be used in photocatalytic dye degradation [6]. Increasing the strategy of the heterojunction formation by coupled with another tungstate. Copper tungstate (CuWO_4) resembles to ZnWO_4 ; it belongs to Wolframite family, exhibiting the band gap of 2.3 eV of n-type oxide semiconductor photocatalyst material. Valence band (VB) composed of O $2p^6$ strongly hybridised states and Cu $3d^{10}$ and conduction band (CB) consists of unoccupied Cu $3d$ states [7]. To facilitate photo-carriers transport, for the photocatalysis, combination of ZnWO_4 and CuWO_4 will give the moderate surface area and optical band gap (Bg). Composite will make the interaction of d^3 and p^2 orbitals by increasing valence band [8].

6.2 Experimental

6.2.1 Preparation of *Spondias mombin* (Hog plum) plant extract

Fresh hog plum leaves were bought at a market located in the Tumakuru district of Karnataka. The leaves were cleaned several times with distilled water. The washed leaves were air-dried for two days at room temperature on sterile blotter paper in the shade. The dried leaves were grinded using blender and then treated in 3 h of reflux extraction. The leftover solvent was removed after the filtration, then dried in desiccators. The filtrate was

then kept at 5-10 °C until the further usage. **Figure 6.1** explains the schematic representation for the process of hog-plum leaves extract.

Figure 6.1 Schematic representation for the process of *Spondias mombin* leaves

6.2.2 Synthesis of ZnWO₄- CuWO₄ nanocomposite

Calculated equal-proportions of 0.1 M Cu (NO₃)₂·6H₂O, Zn (NO₃)₂·6H₂O and H₂WO₄ were dissolved in hog plum leaves extract. All of the mentioned precursors were combined in a mortar and pestle before being transferred into the crucible. For 10 min, the crucible was placed in a warmed combustion chamber at ± 500 °C, where the combustion process takes place. Finally, calcined the formed product at 900 °C for 3 h for the removal of volatile substances. Same way individual ZnWO₄ and CuWO₄ compounds were prepared. **Figure 6.2** represents the synthesis of ZnWO₄- CuWO₄ NPs using hog plum leaves extract.

Figure 6.2 Flow chart representation for the synthesis of ZnWO₄- CuWO₄ NPs using Hog-plum leaves extract

6.3 Results and discussion

6.3.1 Structural and elemental studies

XRD plot of ZnWO₄-CuWO₄ composite has shown in **Figure 6.3**. Inter-planar spacing and their corresponding planes for the respective diffracted planes are 5.8 Å (010), 4.7 Å (100), 2.9 Å(020), 2.3 Å(021), 2 Å (T12), 3 Å (T11), 3.4 Å (T10) corresponds to CuWO₄ triclinic phase as per JCPDS card no #21-307 and 5.7 Å (010), 4.7 Å (100), 3.7 Å (011), 2.9 Å (111), 2.5 Å (021), 2.3 Å (200), 2.2 Å (121), 1.9 Å (022), 1.5 Å (113), 1.3 Å (T32) corresponds to ZnWO₄ monoclinic phase as per JCPDS card no #15-774. Crystallinity nature explained by the sharp characteristic peaks of the nanocomposite. The calculated average crystallite sizes of ZnWO₄, CuWO₄ and ZnWO₄-CuWO₄ compounds are 60, 56 and 30 nm respectively using Debye-Sherrer formula. Binary composite has been confirmed by the presence of both the metal tungstates peaks.

Figure 6.3 XRD pattern of CuWO₄, ZnWO₄ and ZnWO₄- CuWO₄ nanocomposites

Structural range of well-defined Raman modes are referring the crystalline nature of ZnWO₄- CuWO₄ composite shown in **Figure 6.4**. Rayleigh inelastic scattering Raman active modes are designated as A_g/B_g [9]. Primary intense Raman modes of 399, 549, 677, 909 cm⁻¹ might be assigned to both Zinc and Copper tungstates and within 500-600 cm⁻¹ corresponds

to symmetric W-O-W stretching modes. ZnWO_4 characteristic peaks situated at 96, 131, 150, 780 cm^{-1} corresponds to CuWO_4 vibrational modes represents by 183, 224, 284, 317, 538, 482 and 733 cm^{-1} . Presence of six internal and of external modes related to WO_4 octahedra from the composite by Hardcastle and Wachs rules. Stretching modes of copper tungstate resembles to the monoclinic wolffmrite vibrations centered at 399, 549, 677 and 909 cm^{-1} [10].

Figure 6.4 Raman spectrum of ZnWO_4 - CuWO_4 nanocomposite

6.3.2 Surface area and Band gap studies

Nitrogen adsorption/desorption analysis has been carried out at $100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 h in order to examine the surface physiochemical parameters of surface area and pore diameter. The adsorption-desorption isotherm is explained in **Figure 6.5**. The Type II isotherm is identified by a large divergence of the standard isotherm of adsorption. The calculated mean pore diameter and surface area values are 4.3 nm and $63.29\text{ m}^2/\text{g}$, respectively. Pore diameter indicates that the produced particles are mesoporous.

Figure 6.5 N₂ adsorption and desorption isotherm (BET) spectrum of ZnWO₄- CuWO₄ nanocomposite

As per **Figure 6.6 (a)** (UV-DRS graph of ZnWO₄-CuWO₄ nanocomposite), at 230 nm, there has an absorption inflection point, which could be attributed to host lattice absorption. Kubelka-Munk (K-M) theory has been used to calculate the band gap (E_g) energy. The intercept of the tangents of photon energy vs $[F(R_{\infty})/hv]^{1/2}$ has explained in **Figure 6.6 (b)**. The calculated E_g value is 4.5 eV for the binary tungstates.

Figure 6.6 (a) Diffuse reflectance **(b)** Band gap energy plots of ZnWO₄- CuWO₄ nanocomposite

6.3.3 Morphological studies

SEM and TEM have been used to study the topographical information of the $\text{ZnWO}_4\text{-CuWO}_4$ nanocomposite. SEM micrographs of $\text{ZnWO}_4\text{-CuWO}_4$ nanocomposite are shown in **Figure 6.7 (a and b)**. Examination of the SEM image at the 100 μm and 10 nm scales, which are magnified 500 and 4k times, respectively, groups of milli and micro rods are able to seen. Small irregular shaped particles of 289, 347 and 378 nanometers are labelled. EDS spectrum and table are shown in **Figure 6.8**. This confirmed the presence of Zn, W, Cu and O elements.

Figure 6.7 SEM images (a and b) of $\text{ZnWO}_4\text{-CuWO}_4$ nanocomposite

Figure 6.8 EDS spectrum and elemental composition (inset) of $\text{ZnWO}_4\text{-CuWO}_4$ nanocomposite

Figure 6.9 (a and b) portrayed the TEM images of 200, 20 and 2 nm of ZnWO₄-CuWO₄ nanocomposite. Bright spots of the SAED pattern in HR-TEM images **Figure 6.9 (c and d)** confirmed the crystalline nature for the respective planes such as CuWO₄ (T12) ZnWO₄ (010) and CuWO₄ (020).

Figure 6.9 (a, b) TEM images (c) HRTEM (d) SAED pattern of ZnWO₄- CuWO₄ nanocomposite

6.3.4 Photocatalytic dye degradation

Under visible light irradiation, the photocatalytic activity of ZnWO₄-CuWO₄ photocatalyst was examined for the degradation of methylene blue (MB) dye. If the incident photon energy is greater than the threshold bandgap energy (4.5 eV), then the ZnWO₄-CuWO₄ photocatalyst capable to absorb the photon energy to generate holes in the valence band (VB) and electrons in the conduction band (CB). The electrons are then moved into the CuWO₄ conduction band to match the energy level. Binary tungstate catalyst aid in the successful separation of electron-hole pairs by providing sufficient driving force.

If the charge carriers do not undergo recombination, they will begin to migrate near the surface, resulting in oxygen reduction and the formation of peroxides and superoxides. The created holes oxidise the water, forming hydroxyl radicals.

The generated radicals are very reactive and unstable, resulting in dye degradation with the extraction of by-products shown in **Figure 6.10**.

Figure 6.10 Schematic representation of degradation mechanism of the ZnWO₄- CuWO₄ photocatalyst

The size of the particles, the band gap and the surface area are all very important parameters in enhancing photocatalytic activity. During the first step ZnWO_4 , CuWO_4 and $\text{ZnWO}_4\text{-CuWO}_4$ have been analysed by setting 20 mg catalyst and 5 ppm dye at natural pH. Results of the absorption spectra are shown in **Figure 6.11 (a)**, the UV absorption peak centered at 662 nm has steadily diminished for the degradation of MB dye under visible light irradiation for 180 min. **Figure 6.11 (b)** displayed the percentage degradation plots of ZnWO_4 , CuWO_4 and $\text{ZnWO}_4\text{-CuWO}_4$. The obtained degradation efficiency of ZnWO_4 , CuWO_4 and $\text{ZnWO}_4\text{-CuWO}_4$ are 82, 77 and 93 % respectively under visible light irradiation for 180 min for the cationic (MB) dye degradation.

Figure 6.11 (a) UV absorbance plot of $\text{ZnWO}_4\text{-CuWO}_4$ **(b)** Percentage degradation of ZnWO_4 , CuWO_4 and $\text{ZnWO}_4\text{-CuWO}_4$ composites

6.3.5 Factors influencing the photocatalytic dye degradation activity

6.3.5.1 Effect of catalyst dosage and dye quantity

The degradation of MB dye (5 ppm) in the presence of various photocatalyst dosages ranging from 10, 20, 30 and 40 mg of $\text{ZnWO}_4\text{-CuWO}_4$ catalyst. As shown in **Figure 6.12 (a)**, the obtained percentage degradations are 79, 92, 70 and 65 respectively. When the catalyst dosage has increased from 10 to 20 mg, the percentage degradation of MB increases linearly. The photocatalytic activity decreases as the catalyst dosage increases further. The initial boost in degrading efficiency due to increase in active sites on the photocatalyst's surface. When the catalyst dose is higher than its optimum, degradation efficiency suffers because of turbidity in the reaction medium, which reduces the light penetration. The variation of dye concentration with the constant catalytic load has explained in **Figure 6.12 (b)**. The MB dye concentrations of 5, 10, 15 and 20 ppm resulted in 92, 80, 65 and 50 percent degradations

respectively. Under visible light irradiation, the 20 mg of $\text{ZnWO}_4\text{-CuWO}_4$ photocatalyst and 5 ppm showed a high percentage of degradation, as shown in the above data. As a result, optimising dye dosage and volume may play a critical role in improving the efficiency of further trials.

Figure 6.12 Percentage degradation of $\text{ZnWO}_4\text{-CuWO}_4$ (a) Catalyst variation (b) ppm

6.3.5.2 Effect of pH and recyclability

The adsorption performance between catalyst and dye has greatly impacted by the pH of the degradation medium. The experiment has carried out at a catalyst dosage of 20 mg $\text{ZnWO}_4\text{-CuWO}_4$ and 5 ppm MB dye concentration for the evaluation of different pH values ranging from 2-12 as shown in **Figure 6.13 (a)** under visible light. The percentage degradation values of 27, 85, 80, 50, 90 and 97 for the pH values 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 respectively. The MB dye deteriorated swiftly in the pH 12 and 10 basic environment due to the availability of more OH radicals. The percentage degradation increased even in the acidic medium at 4 and 6. Therefore $\text{ZnWO}_4\text{-CuWO}_4$ nanophotocatalyst capable to degrade MB dye in the acidic medium at 4 and 6. **Figure 6.13 (b)** explains the recyclability graph. The number of cycles vs. degradation (%) for four times under visible light interactions. To examine stability, the catalyst has been used even after each degrading cycle had completed. Centrifugated the collected sample to separate the photocatalyst from the dye absorbents. The settled sample has dried for the further usage. The procedure has been repeated for the next three cycles continuously under visible light, the $\text{ZnWO}_4\text{-CuWO}_4$ catalyst deteriorated 89, 83, 78 and 75 % for the 1, 2, 3 and 4 cycles, respectively.

Figure 6.13 Percentage degradation of ZnWO₄- CuWO₄ (a) pH variation (b) Recyclability of over 4 cycles

6.3.5.3 Kinetics of photocatalytic degradation

The first order reaction kinetics of the MB dye for the ZnWO₄, CuWO₄ and ZnWO₄-CuWO₄ representing by the below equation

$$\ln\left(\frac{C_0}{C}\right) = kt \quad (6.4)$$

Where C_0 and C represents the initial and particular concentrations of the MB dye after the degradation with respect to time 't' and 'k' represents the rate constant. In the plot (**Figure 6.14**) straight line represents the first order equation of the degradation. Rate constant is the obtained slope of straight line. Calculated rate constants of ZnWO₄, CuWO₄ and ZnWO₄-CuWO₄ are 1.18×10^{-2} , 0.78×10^{-2} and $2.71 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$ respectively. Higher rate constant of the binary tungstate represents the degradation efficiency towards MB dye.

Figure 6.14 Reaction kinetics of ZnWO₄- CuWO₄ nanocomposite

Table 6.1 explains the photocatalytic performance of ZnWO₄, CuWO₄ photocatalysts. G.V. Geetha et. al., have synthesised ZnWO₄ NPs by co-precipitation method with the influence of 30 mL of solvent volume. The degradation efficiency achieved 81 % for the MB dye, due to nanopores and more active species [12]. X.Hu et al., prepared CuWO₄ nanochains and NPs by solvothermal method. CuWO₄ NPs have exhibited 86 % degradation efficiency for the MB dye after 90 min under UV-vis irradiation [13]. Sol-gel synthesised ZnWO₄ photocatalyst towards MB dye in UV irradiation. They have obtained the band gap energy of 3.20 eV and rate constant $k = 1.62 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$ due to the calcination temperature of 500 °C and maintenance of pH-6 [11]. Tandem CuWO₄/Cu_{1-x}Zn_xWO₄/ZnWO₄ is good photocatalyst through the formation of sandwiched heterojunction [14].

Table 6.1 Photocatalytic performance of ZnWO ₄ , CuWO ₄ photocatalysts						
Sl. No.	Photocatalysts	Synthesis method	Dye	Light	Degradation (%)	References
1	ZnWO ₄	Co-precipitation	Methylene blue	UV	81	[12]
2	CuWO ₄	Solvothermal	Methylene blue	UV-Vis	86	[13]
3	ZnWO ₄	Sol-gel	Methylene blue	UV	Rate constant (k=1.6×10 ⁻²)	[11]
4	CuWO ₄ /Cu _{1-x} Zn _x WO ₄ /ZnWO ₄	Precipitation	Rhodamine B	Vis	80	[14]
3	ZnWO ₄ - CuWO ₄	Combustion	Methylene blue	Vis	92 (k=2.71×10 ⁻²)	This work

Binary tungstates of $\text{ZnWO}_4\text{-CuWO}_4$ showed high surface area ($63.29 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$), crystallite size (30 nm), uniform dispersion of particles and band gap (4.5 eV) influenced to degrade 92 % of MB dye under visible light irradiation in 180 min.

6.3.6 Electrochemical oxidation of nitrite sensing

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) and linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) are the two techniques used for the nitrite sensing analysis, in the range of 10 to 100 mV/s with $1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ sensitivity for the $\text{ZnWO}_4\text{-CuWO}_4$ modified GCE. **Figure 6.15 (a)** demonstrates the cyclic voltammogram of a $\text{ZnWO}_4\text{-CuWO}_4$ modified electrode used to detect 5 mM nitrite. An oxidation peak current response at 16 μA has observed for the bare glassy carbon electrode. The individual tungstates CuWO_4 (38 μA), ZnWO_4 (37 μA) showed sluggish electron transfer response compared to binary tungstate $\text{ZnWO}_4\text{-CuWO}_4$ (52 μA) modified GCE. The enhancement in the current response due to the increased electrocatalytic activity by the availability of more active sites from a larger surface area. The irreversible electrochemical oxidation reaction represents the nitrite to nitrate.

Figure 6.15 (b) showed an overlaid LSV of $\text{ZnWO}_4\text{-CuWO}_4$ modified GCE for the detection of nitrite within concentration range of 100- 900 μL in KCl buffer of pH 7 of 50 mV/s scan rate. The oxidation peak current increases linearly with the increase in nitrite solution, according to LSV curves. The detection limit of 26.09 μM has been obtained by the calibration plot (**Figure 6.15 (c)**) of anodic peak current against nitrite concentration. According to the aforementioned discussion, it is understanding that the $\text{ZnWO}_4\text{-CuWO}_4$ modified GCE exhibited the enhancement of electrocatalytic activity for the detection of nitrite. Faster diffusion of the nitrite on the electrode surface responsible for the good sensing property of the binary tungstates. $\text{ZnWO}_4\text{-CuWO}_4$ modified GCE is also one of the good substitutes for detecting nitrites.

J. Vinoth kumar et al., prepared 2D cerium tungstate nanosheets for the detection of nitrite ions. Very low detection limit of 0.02–986 mM was detectable using CeW_2O_9 modified GCE by faster electro oxidation process due to large surface area [15]. Limited tungstates research papers available for the detection of nitrite. Other tungstates such as manganese, zinc, tin tungstates are used in gas sensors [16-18], silver tungstate is used in the detection ethanol, ammonia and acetone gases [19].

Figure 6.15(a) Cyclic voltammogram **(b)** Linear sweep voltammetry **(c)** Calibration graph of ZnWO₄- CuWO₄ electrocatalyst

6.4 Conclusion

To conclude, binary tungstates of ZnWO₄-CuWO₄ was synthesised through cost effective, single step combustion method using green fuel of *Spondias mombin* (Hog plum) leaves. The analysis revealed that the well crystalline, high surface area of 63.29 m²/g, mesoporous nanocomposite exhibits the good photocatalytic properties due to the availability of more active sites that involve in the catalytic activity. Compared to individual tungstates of ZnWO₄ and CuWO₄, binary tungstate of ZnWO₄-CuWO₄ nanocomposite projected with the superior degradation percentage of 93 under visible light in 180 min and it could degrade in acidic medium. Higher anodic peak current of the ZnWO₄-CuWO₄ signifies the better electrocatalytic activity compared to individual tungstates due to large surface area of ZnWO₄-CuWO₄ nanocomposite capable to detect up to 26.09 µM towards 5 mM nitrite.

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CHAPTER - VII

Summary and Future prospects

Summary

Chapter 1 discusses the introduction of nanotechnology, nanomaterials classification and its properties, Li-ion batteries, photocatalytic dye degradation and nitrite sensing. Also, covers the detailed literature survey.

Chapter 2 provides various experimental methods and characterization techniques (spectroscopic and morphological) of the prepared nanomaterials. Besides included the explanation of energy gap, surface area and thermal analysis.

Chapter 3 deals with the synthesis of Ta₂O₅ nanoparticles by sonochemical method. Morphology of the materials confirmed by SEM and TEM. Ta₂O₅ NPs maintained stable discharge capacity even after 200 cycles at C/10 rate. The high percentage of degradation of methylene blue (MB) dye is possible due to large surface area and a modest bandgap. Glassy carbon electrode (GCE) modified Ta₂O₅ NPs capable to detect 5 mM nitrite with lower detection limit.

Chapter 4 provides the synthesis of h-MoO₃ hexagonal rods by reflux technique. Prepared h-MoO₃ hexagonal rods have been characterised structurally, morphologically and electrochemically. The h-MoO₃ electrode has delivered outstanding discharge capacity at a current rate of C/15 over 100 cycles as well as maintained stability. Achieved lower detection limit by h-MoO₃ modified GCE.

Chapter 5 gives the synthesis of binary composite SnO₂-CuO synthesis by sonochemical method. The synthesized material was characterized by XRD, FTIR, Raman, SEM and TEM. Band gap (E_g), surface area and thermal stability were analysed. This nanocomposite was delivered stable capacity even at higher 2C rate. SnO₂-CuO modified GCE has analysed for nitrite sensing and photocatalytic dye degradation.

Chapter 6 deals with the synthesis, characterization of binary tungstates towards photocatalytic dye degradation and electrochemical nitrite sensing. Synthesis of ZnWO₄-CuWO₄ by *Spondias mombin* (Hog plum) leaves assisted combustion method. Due to high surface area binary tungstates capable to degrade high percentage of MB dye under visible light and showed lower detection limit towards 5 mM nitrite sensing.

Chapter 7 summarizes the obtained results in the present investigation and scope of the future work.

Future prospects

- ❖ Lithium-ion battery can be extended to Na-ion battery K-ion battery, Li-air battery, Li-S battery and other advanced batteries. Pseudocapacitive materials and binary composites can improve the electrochemical performance by mitigating the volume expansion.
- ❖ Composites including carbon derivatives are very good photocatalytic materials towards the removal of toxic dye effluents. The composite nanomaterials can extend the application to H₂ generation through water splitting process.
- ❖ Environment friendly green fuels mediated nanomaterials may be scaled up to low-cost methods for the wide range of applications.
- ❖ Electrochemical nitrite sensing can explore with composite materials of carbon derivatives.

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ANNEXURE - I

List of Publications and Conferences Presented/ Attended

Research Publications

1. **V. Pavitra**, B. M. Praveen, G. Nagaraju, Shashanka R, Energy Storage, Photocatalytic and Electrochemical Nitrite Sensing of Ultrasound-Assisted Stable Ta₂O₅ Nanoparticles, Topics in Catalysis, 2022 (**IF- 2.781**)
2. **V. Pavitra**, Udayabhanu, R. Viswanatha, B. M. Praveen, G. Nagaraju Sonochemical synthesis of SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite: Diverse applications on Li-ion battery, Electrochemical sensing and Photocatalytic activity, Journal of Material science: Material science in Electronics, 31 (2020) 8737–8749 (**IF- 2.478**),
3. Udayabhanu[#], **Veerabhadrachar Pavitra**[#], Marappa Shivanna, Fahad A. Alharthi, Beekannahalli Mokshanatha Praveen, Yaled Thippeswamy Ravikiran, Kullaiah Byrappa, Ganganagappa Nagaraju, High capacitive h-MoO₃ hexagonal rods and its applications towards lithium-ion battery, humidity and nitrite sensing, International Journal of Energy Research, 45 (2021) 17315-17326 (**IF- 5.164**) (**#: Equal contribution**)
4. **V. Pavitra**, H.P. Divya, B.M. Praveena, G. Nagaraju, Udayabhanu, Radish (*Raphanus sativus*) leaves mediated CuO-NiO nanocomposite for photocatalytic activity (Accepted, optical and sensor characteristics of nanocomposites, 2022 h-index-34)

Papers communicated

1. **Pavitra**, B. M. Praveen, G. Nagaraju, Exploring the Spndias mombin (Hog plum) mediated ZnWO₄- CuWO₄ composite nanoparticles for photocatalysis and nitrite sensing (**Materials Chemistry and Physics MATCHEMPHYS-D-22-03200- Under review**)
2. **Pavitra**, Isha Soni, B. M. Praveen, G. Nagaraju, Brief review on carbon derivatives based ternary metal oxide composite electrode materials for lithium-ion batteries, (**IONICS-2022-0515- Under review**)

Other papers contributions

1. Udayabhanu[#], V. Pavitra[#], S.C. Sharma, G. Nagaraju, *Epigallocatechin gallate* (EGCG) assisted combustion synthesis of V₂O₅ nanoparticles for Li-ion battery, *International Journal of Ionics*, 26 (2020) 1203-1210 (**IF-2.961**) (**#: Equal contribution**)
2. Dawoud, T. M. S., Pavitra, V., Ahmad, P., Syed, A., & Nagaraju, G. Photocatalytic degradation of an organic dye using Ag doped ZrO₂ nanoparticles: Milk powder facilitated eco-friendly synthesis. *Journal of King Saud University - Science*. 32 (2020) 1872-1878 (**IF- 3.829**)

Paper Presented International/ National Conferences

1. International conference on New Horizons and Trends in Chemical Sciences (ICNHTCS-2022) organized by Dept. of Chemistry, Dada Ramachand Bakhru Sindhu Mahavidyalaya, Nagpur Chapter during 25th-26th March 2022 (**Oral Presentation**)
2. Virtual national workshop on Advanced Materials for Energy and Environment Applications (AMEEA 2020), organized by Yogi Vemana University, Kadapa, Andhra Pradesh, through online mode Dec 21st to 23rd 2020
3. International webinar on Recent Advances in synthesizing the Material for the Application in Natural Science, organized by Model Govt. Degree College Charar-i-Sharief Dist. Budgam Kashmir, through online mode on 28-09-2020
4. Webinar on Energy conversion and storage, organized by CIT, Chennai, through online mode on 29-06-2020
5. International Webinar lecture series on Energy Physics, organized by Dept. of Physics, Kumbakonam, Tamilnadu, through online mode on 23-06-2020
6. International 107th Women's Science Congress organized by DST, Ministry of Science & Technology, Govt. of India held on Jan 3rd to 7th 2020 at University of Agricultural Sciences, GKVK, Bengaluru
7. International 107th Indian Science Congress organized by DST, Ministry of Science & Technology, Govt. of India held on Jan 3rd to 7th 2020

8. National conference on Advanced Lithium-ion Batteries (NALIBST) organized by The Electrochemical Society of India and IPC IISc, Bengaluru, held on 27th-28th December 2019
9. International Conference on “Nanotechnology” in Srinivas University, Mangalore, held on 18th and 19th October 2019 (**Oral Presentation**)
10. National conference on “Advanced Materials for Health, Energy and Environment” JSS University, Mysore, held on 6th & 7th September, 2019 (**Received Best Oral Presentation Award**)

Energy Storage, Photocatalytic and Electrochemical Nitrite Sensing of Ultrasound-Assisted Stable Ta₂O₅ Nanoparticles

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Abstract

This paper reports the advanced Ta₂O₅ nanomaterial, prepared by ultrasonication via DMSO (Dimethyl sulfoxide) as a solvent; towards the rechargeable Li-ion battery photocatalytic dye degradation and electrochemical nitrite sensing applications. Elemental and structural confirmation of Ta₂O₅ nanoparticles (NPs) has been characterized by XRD and FTIR. Morphological and compositions are analyzed by SEM with EDS and HRTEM. Surface area, bandgap, and thermal stability results are obtained by BET, DRS, and TGA-DTA analysis. Diffracted peaks are confirmed the orthorhombic phase. FTIR confirmed the presence of the Ta–O stretching vibration band. Ta₂O₅ anode has maintained the reversible discharge capacity of 192 mAh g⁻¹ for 200 cyclic rotations at a C/10 rate. Furthermore, Ta₂O₅ NPs have also exemplified the good photocatalytic activity against Methylene blue dye under visible light irradiation. Nitrite (NO₂⁻) sensing has been performed using Ta₂O₅ NPs modified glassy carbon electrode as an additional study.

Keywords Ta₂O₅ NPs · Ultrasonication method · HRTEM · Lithium-ion battery · Photocatalytic activity · Electrochemical nitrite sensing

1 Introduction

Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) are most hopeful at the efficient storage of electrochemical energy for prominent and exceptional applications in automobiles, smart grids, and portable electronic devices. The significant development of LIBs rely on the advancement of electrode materials [1–3]. LIBs have superior gravimetric and volumetric energy density due to higher cell voltage and wide operating temperature range [4, 5]. Lithium-ion technology is completely rooted in

developing novel materials with good battery performance. The stability and capacity retention mainly dependent on active substances such as metals with oxides, sulfides, and alloys are being contemplated [6–10]. Greater capacity could be anticipated through the conversion and insertion process, which could be implemented by the electrode materials made up of metal oxides [11–13]. Metal oxide nanoparticles (NPs) have capable to tune the physicochemical properties for significant results in diverse applications [14–21]. Trending fuel cells and supercapacitors have also gained much attention due to their high energy density applications. These days Ta₂O₅ electrode material has been considered for energy storage application because of the high extrinsic pseudocapacitance. Ta₂O₅ is an advanced metal oxide anode that is innocuous and for Li⁺ storage its theoretical discharge capacity of 482 mAh g⁻¹. Ta₂O₅ anode has some drawbacks such as lower conductivity and variable plateau while charging–discharging [22]. Fu et al. have fabricated through reactive pulsed laser deposited amorphous Ta₂O₅ thin films used as negative electrode material for LIBs with a specified discharge capacity (411 mAh g⁻¹) [23]. Ta₂O₅ thin films of amorphous nanostructure have been reported with the Lithium ions insertion–extraction characteristics [24, 25]. Long Pan et al. have discussed the extrinsic pseudocapacitance by

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SPECIAL ISSUE RESEARCH ARTICLE

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High capacitive h-MoO₃ hexagonal rods and its applications towards lithium ion battery, humidity and nitrite sensing

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Summary

In this paper, the authors have investigated a suitable material for rechargeable lithium-ion battery, which poses a challenge to the researchers in the search for alternate electrode materials. An analysis of humidity as well as nitrite sensing application, the potential of this material has been reported. MoO₃ can reversibly store large amounts of Li; it can be a potential alternative electrode among currently existing anode materials. The self-assembled hexagonal rods of h-MoO₃ as flowers have been synthesized via a simple and facile low temperature reflux method. The measured mean crystallite size and band gap (E_g) of h-MoO₃ hexagonal crystalline structure are 52 nm and 3.48 eV as per the XRD and UV-vis DRS studies respectively. Hexagonal rod shaped h-MoO₃ anodes exhibit remarkable electrochemical stability, recyclability, high rate capability; which produce the initial discharge capacity of 1869 mAh g⁻¹ and then the capacity retained around 619 mAh g⁻¹ at 100th cycle of charge-discharge profile by applying the current rate of C/15. This simple and novel material synthesis provides unique morphology of hexagonal rods shaped h-MoO₃ flowers; and this scheme provides the facile pathways which enable the ease of electron transportation. The sensing activity of modified glassy electrode of h-MoO₃ has shown a limit of detection of 0.196 μM for 1 mM nitrite sensing. It also showed high humidity sensing response of 97.9 %, and indicated that the h-MoO₃ flowery material is well suitable for industrial applications.

KEYWORDS

h-MoO₃ hexagonal rods, humidity sensor, lithium ion battery, reflux method

1 | INTRODUCTION

Energy comprised of its sources and effective fulfilment of the global needs. Among the primary dependent energy

Udayabhanu and V. Pavitra contributed equally to this study.

sources (fossil fuels, nuclear, hydro, solar, geothermal and bio-fuels), the non-renewable and renewable energy sources come with a downside for the large scale exhaling of energy. These non-renewable energy sources have to be harvested by mining; it causes the combustion, carbon emissions and nuclear wastage. Eventually, it leads to

Sonochemical synthesis of SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite: diverse applications on Li-ion battery, electrochemical sensing and photocatalytic activity

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Abstract

To develop the durability and the reversibility of SnO₂-based anodic materials for lithium-ion batteries, a binary composite of SnO₂-CuO nanoparticles is obtained by effective ultrasonication method. Well-dispersed and high surface area particles are obtained by ultrasonication method. SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite is also analysed for nitrite sensing and photocatalytic dye degradation applications. Synthesised composite is well characterised for the confirmation of elemental presence, crystallinity, surface area, topography and elemental composition. SnO₂-CuO anode exhibits high initial discharge capacity of 1365 mA h g⁻¹ and maintains 252 mA h g⁻¹ at 100th cycle for C/10 rate. Stability of multistep electrochemical reversible reactions is confirmed by CV curves during the lithiation/de-lithiation process and also it retains 90 mA h g⁻¹ capacity at higher 2C rate. This study is the first one to report that SnO₂-CuO modified glassy carbon electrode for the sensing of 1 mM nitrite. It has proved the sensing activity with a detection limit of 0.82 μM. SnO₂-CuO nanocomposite is also capable to degrade 86% of Methylene blue (MB) dye in 150 min under UV light interactions. Enhancement in the results attributed the synergistic effects of well-dispersed and nanoscaled composite particles.

1 Introduction

The secondary rechargeable lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) are very important in powering the electric devices, which play a major role in our day-to-day life. Foremost these batteries will reduce the consumption of depleting fuels in turn usage of electric vehicles (EVs) rather than petrol/diesel vehicles

[1]. Batteries are directly fulfilling our energy requirements and indirectly will protect our livelihood from prevailing global warming, through environmental pollution in energy harnessing. LIBs hold much energy as twice as their weight ratio. In this, self-discharge rate is much lower and priming is not required when they receive first charge, so this impacted LIBs to popularise commercially. Research on LIBs includes development of anode and cathode battery materials, for extracting high capacity with high energy density [2]. Commercialised common cathode materials are Lithium Cobalt Oxide (LiCoO₂), Lithium Manganese Oxide (LiMnO₂), Lithium Iron Phosphate (LiFePO₄), Lithium Nickel Manganese Cobalt Oxide (LiNiMnCoO₂) and graphite as anode in all batteries [3, 4]. Graphite is not suitable for the next generation electric devices and vehicles due to low gravimetric capacity (372 mA h g⁻¹) [5]. Meanwhile, LIBs suffer from stability, safety, rate capability and capacity issues, which hinders the performance [6]. This has motivated the researchers to come up with the new advanced electrode materials. Recently binary, tertiary metal oxide composites are in trend to overcome from the above-mentioned drawbacks of LIBs. To strengthen the intrinsic qualities of the batteries, we are concentrating on the anode materials to replace the default graphite anode to achieve the

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ORIGINAL PAPER

Epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG)-assisted combustion synthesis of V_2O_5 nanoparticles for Li-ion battery

Udayabhanu¹ · V. Pavitra¹ · S. C. Sharma² · G. Nagaraju¹

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Abstract

Nanometric orthorhombic vanadium pentoxide (V_2O_5) cathode has been fabricated via a facile simple and single step combustion method by the utilization of *Epigallocatechin gallate* (EGCG) tea extract fuel in order to tailor the optimized electrochemical properties. Structural and surface morphologies of V_2O_5 nanoparticles (NPs) are examined by XRD, Raman spectroscopy, TGA, SEM, and HRTEM. The electrochemical performance of synthesized V_2O_5 NPs has studied towards the lithium-ion batteries (LIBs). Various parameters like charge-discharge, cyclic voltammogram (CV) columbic efficiency, and rate capability are studied. The nanometer V_2O_5 particles show the reversible capacity of 222 mA h g^{-1} after 50 cycles. The formation of lithium intercalation compound (LiV_2O_5) was confirmed by ex situ XRD studies after the continuous 50 charge/discharge cycles as the proof of stability. V_2O_5 cathode has performed stable performance by the electrochemical analysis.

Keywords EGCG · Combustion · Vanadium pentoxide · Li-ion battery

Introduction

Rechargeable batteries are potential and versatile source of energy for the present impending worldwide usage and also benign for nature. In order to reduce the high energy needs and to overcome from the dependency of unpredictable natural energy sources, batteries are attracted because of high power density, energy density, and improved stable long cycle life. These electrochemical cells affect neither from the climatic issues nor from the installation and distribution costs. Since three decades, the research has been upgrading on electrode materials to achieve better features and to attain concentration by using the state-of-the-art of booming nanoscience and technology.

Anode and cathode of battery materials directly participate or indirectly help catalytic action in an electrochemical

conversion process. In addition, they even promote to enhance properties to achieve high capacity, high columbic efficiency, and low toxicity, mainly to avoid unwanted additives. Here, we emphasized on the powder form of nanometric oxides, which exhibits unique novel physical and chemical properties due to density, surface to volume ratio, and spatial confinement [1]. Specialized local and collective features are produce among the transition metal oxide for the diverse potential electrochemical devices in order to mitigate energy crisis.

Lithium-concentrated batteries are intensively and extensively attracted, to reach the above requirement. Large potential window facilitated the vanadium pentoxide to act as cathode towards lithiation/de-lithiation among the currently available cathode materials $LiCoO_2$, $LiMn_2O_4$, $LiFePO_4$, and $LiNi_{1-x-y}Co_xMn_yO_2$. Moreover, vanadium pentoxide has special properties such as high co-efficient of thermal resistance, abundant sources, better safety, and well-studied intercalation compound due to its large surface area and also easy transportation of charge [2]. The researchers have started extensive studies on vanadium oxides since the discovery of cost effective VO_x nanotubes [3, 4]. Synthesis of vanadium oxides leads to the reduction of V^{5+} valence ions quickly and tends to form mixed ions phases such as V^{5+} , V^{4+} , and V^{3+} ions and habitually forms the mixture of various phases of VO_x or V_2O_x . Oxygen vacancies on the surface make it easier for the faster diffusion of lithium ions [5, 6]. Nonetheless, if size of the

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